

INFERENCE OF VISUAL INSPECTION WITH ACETIC ACID ON CERVIX: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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**“INFERENCE OF VISUAL INSPECTION WITH ACETIC ACID ON
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ABBREVIATIONS

VIA	Visual inspection with acetic acid
CIN	Cervical intraepithelial neoplasia
AIS	Adenocarcinoma in situ
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
WHO	World health organization
SCJ	Squamo-columnar junction
HPV	Human papillomavirus
LEEP	Loop electrosurgical excision procedure
LLETZ	Large- loop excision of the transformation zone
ASCUS	Atypical squamous cells of unknown significance
PAP SMEAR	Papanicolaou Smear
LBC	Liquid based cytology
PHC	Primary Health-Care

SD	Standard deviation
UNEE	Unaided naked eye examination

ABSTRACT

Cervical cancer is an important health problem. It is the commonest cancer in females. Due to lack of awareness, many women end up with the advanced stage of cancer. Cervical cancer screening is a practice used by both developed and developing countries.

Visual inspection with acetic acid (VIA) is a primary screening test in low resource settings for detection of cervical premalignant and cervical carcinoma.

Cervicitis results in false-positive VIA. ⁽¹⁾ The decision to provide immediate treatment depends on the lesion size, suspicion of invasion, and the examiner's expertise.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

To study the spectrum and proportion of cervical histopathologies in aceto-white areas of the cervix.

METHODOLOGY

This is a cross-sectional study. The women who fulfil the inclusion criteria will be studied. Consents will be taken once the patient is willing for this study .

In lithotomy position per speculum examination is done. Sterile Cusco's self-retaining vaginal speculum is inserted and cervix is inspected by naked eye. Acetic acid 3-5% is applied to the cervical area and observed for acetowhite lesions after 1 minute.

From these acetowhite areas , cervical biopsy is taken from these areas and suspicious lesions and sent to a pathologist for histopathology evaluation. These histopathological diagnosis correlated with VIA findings. The proportion of cervical pathologies will be seen in this study in low resource settings.

RESULTS

The total participants of 880, age ranging between 30-49 years old. Incidence of VIA positive was 8.4%, in that incidence of chronic cervicitis was 7% respectively. Incidence of premalignant lesion was 0.6%. Incidence of cervical carcinoma was 0.1%. The factors associated with a positive VIA was cervicitis.

CONCLUSION

The accuracy of VIA results may be impacted by the presence of cervicitis. This finding may be especially significant in low-resource countries where cervical cancer screenings are more frequently conducted using visual inspection techniques. The incidence of cervical pre malignancy and malignancy lesions was 0.6% and 0.1% respectively in the population being studied with VIA. These findings have substantial consequences for the effective provision of services in cervical screening tests in settings with limited resources.

KEY WORDS

Cervical cancer, VIA, cervical cancer screening tests.

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INTRODUCTION

Cervical cancer is an important health problem. It is the commonest cancer in females. Due to lack of awareness, many women end up with the last stage of cancer. Cervical cancer screening is a practice used by both developed and developing countries.

Cervical Cancer is the second most common cancer among women in India.⁽⁴⁾ It is the only preventable cancer and it can be detected in the pre-cancerous phase.

Visual inspection with acetic acid (VIA) is a quick, low-cost screening test that can be used in conjunction with quick treatments for early cervical lesions. It has a modest sensitivity and specificity. As test administrators, nurses or health professionals can be trained; the results are made promptly available. In many low-resource places where it is challenging to maintain high-quality cytology programmes, VIA is practical. Few studies show VIA is a simple and affordable screening test with acceptable sensitivity and specificity in the range 50-88.6% and 66.7-89.7%, respectively, in a research setting.⁽¹¹⁾

VIA is an appropriate substitute in a situation with limited resources due to the fact that it offers immediate effects and requires little in the way of resources (both financial and human).

Certain kinds of human papillomavirus infection are the main cause of cervical cancer. An elevated risk of cervical cancer is associated with nearly 15 different strains of human papillomavirus. Human papillomavirus types 16 and 18 are the most prevalent viruses that cause cervical cancer.

Any one form of human papillomavirus, which is quite common in sexually active women, is what causes cervical infections.

Only a small fraction of human papillomavirus infections proceed to cervical cancer and resolve spontaneously after two to four years. The women present high parity, immunological suppression, more sexual partners over the course of a lifetime, and continuous use of contraceptives are risk factors that are altered by a variety of conditions, including cigarette smoking and chronic infection.

The 35 to 50 year old high risk age group is regarded as the core element of successful screening programmes. Low resource settings can use a simple and affordable solution.

One round of HPV DNA testing considerably decreased the incidence of new cases of cervical cancer and mortality, according to a recent clinical trial conducted in rural India as a resource region. Two vaccines offer protection against 70% of the viruses that cause cervical cancer. The high cost of vaccines in developing nations is a major obstacle to widespread usage.

Incidence

The current population of India is -1,601,441,607,688 as of Friday, September 16, 2022, based on Worldometer elaboration of the latest United Nations data, while the number of females accounts for 48.05% of the total population at 675 million.⁽³⁾

In India, cancer of the cervix uteri is the 2nd most common cancer with an incidence rate of 9.4% (123,907 cases) and the second leading cause of death with a mortality rate of 9.1% (77,348) as per GLOBOCAN 2020.⁽⁴⁾

The age standardized incidence rate per 100,000 population was 18 while the 5 year prevalence rate across all age's was 42.82 per 1 lakh population.⁽⁴⁾ As per the National Cancer Registry Programme, cancer of breast and cervix uteri was the most common cancers among females.

Cervical cancer accounted for 6-29% of all cancers among women in India. Papumpare district in the state of Arunachal Pradesh, India had the highest incidence rate of cervical cancer (27.7) in Asia.⁽⁵⁾

The majority of the patients with cancer were diagnosed at the locally advanced stage for breast (57 %), cervix uteri (60 %), head and neck (66.6%), and stomach (50.8%).

Cancer, whereas in lung cancer, distant metastasis was predominant among males (44 %) and females (47.6%).⁽⁵⁾

Structure of the cervix

Cervix is lower fibromuscular part of the uterus, 3-4 cm long and cervical diameter is around 2.5 cm in diameter. This is not a fixed measurement and will vary with age, menstrual status and fertility. For parous women, the cervix is voluminous and has a large ostium, which looks like a gaping transverse slit. In nulliparous women, the cervical os appears as a small circular opening in the cervix.

Cervical epithelium :

The cervix consists of the endocervix and the ectocervix. The ectocervix is the most visible part and distal to the external os. Usually endocervical lining is invisible.

Figure 1 : The Uterine cervix.

Figure 2: The portio vaginalis is the part of the cervix that is visible during a speculum examination .⁽⁶⁾

The endocervix is lined by a single layer of columnar epithelium with a firm basal nucleus .Visual inspection reveals that it is red because the glandular epithelium easily reveals the vasculature inside the epithelium. Papillary projections are created when the endocervical epithelium is pushed into many longitudinal folds that protrude into the cervical canal.

Endocervical crypts can occasionally develop as a result of papillary projections invading the cervical stroma. Under this, there is a layer of cubical or reserve cells from which it is thought that new surface cells arise and undergo metaplasia.

In columnar cells, glycogenation and mitoses don't exist. Due to the absence of intracytoplasmic glycogen, lugol's iodine application does not cause the columnar epithelium to change colour.

Non-keratinizing glycogen-containing squamous stratified ectocervix four-layered epithelium are:

1. Basal layer
2. Parabasal layer
3. Intermediate layer
4. Superficial layer

The basal layer is composed of a single layer of basal cells with a nucleus that is darkly stained and minimal cytoplasm. The basement membrane is connected to these cells. Straight lines define the epithelium-stromal junction.

The parabasal cells, which contain a substantial dark-staining nucleus and little basophilic cytoplasm, are the next layer of cells below basal layer. They continue to proliferate, producing an intermediate layer of polygonal cells with plenty of cytoplasm and tiny, rounded nuclei. They create a basket-weave design.

The superficial cells, which are flattened cells with tiny, dense pyknotic nuclei and translucent cytoplasm, make up the next layer.

Figure 3: ECTOCERVIX LAYERS

There is a lot of glycogen in the surface and intermediate levels. The superficial and intermediate cells' glycogenation is a marker of proper maturation. Oestrogen hormone is necessary for squamous epithelium to mature. As a result of the lack of oestrogen, glycogenation and maturation are not completed. Epithelium becomes very thin and atrophic after menopause, as the epithelium does not mature after the parabasal cells.

Junction between the columnar epithelium and original squamous epithelium which is present during the embryogenesis and intra uterine life is squamocolumnar junction.

Figure 4: Anatomy of cervix

The squamocolumnar junction (SCJ) is situated relatively near the external os throughout childhood. The cervix enlarges during adolescence and the reproductive years, which causes the endocervical canal to enlarge as well. As a result, the endocervix's columnar epithelium turns toward the ectocervix. Ectropion, also known as entropy, is the medical term for this ailment, which manifests itself visually as a reddish-looking ectocervix. As a result, the Original SCJ is far from the

external os in later periods, and the ectropion is more obvious throughout the reproductive years.

Figure 5: Squamocolumnar junction (SCJ) ⁽³⁹⁾

The acidic vaginal environment disturbs the mucus buffering function in the columnar epithelium. As a result, the columnar epithelium is destroyed and finally replaced by squamous metaplastic cells. Metaplasia typically commences at the original squamo columnar junction and progresses centripetally in the os during the reproductive years and during the peri-menopausal age, and in the direction of the external os. The new SCJ then advances towards the external os. The new SCJ will be situated at varied distances from the os over the course of a person's life.

NATURAL HISTORY OF THE DISEASE

Cervical intraepithelial neoplasia is the premalignant condition of the cervix. These abnormalities are squamous. CIN can be a high- or low-grade lesion. Women with low grade lesions have little chance of developing cancer, whereas those with high grade lesions are most at risk.

Because screening is less accessible and HPV vaccines are more expensive, cervical cancer rates are disproportionately higher in less developed nations. 11 The majority of instances of cervical cancer are linked to HPV infection, with HPV-16 and HPV-18 identified as the most carcinogenic subtypes, respectively accounting for nearly 50% and 10% of cases.⁽⁷⁾

HPV is a non-enveloped double stranded circular DNA virus with a diameter of 5nm. The genome is approximately 8kb in size and encased in icosahedral capsid which is composed of 72 capsomeres. The capsid comprise of an outer protein coat which consist of two capsid proteins; L1 (major) and L2 (minor).⁽¹³⁾

Figure 6: Human papillomavirus on the surface of a cell. A model is built using data of viral macromolecular structure from Protein Data Bank (PDB 3J6R). Image Credit: Kateryna Kon / Shutterstock.⁽³⁸⁾

The juvenile basal layer of the epithelium is where the Human Papilloma Virus first manifests its harmful effects. Typically, the HPV DNA linked to benign tumours is extrachromosomal. The superficial and intermediate epithelial layers levels of viral DNA because the papilloma virus coexists with the process of epithelial cell development. Koilocytes are produced when virus particles build up in the top layer of the epithelium and have a cytopathic effect. These cells have

damaged nuclear membranes, misplaced cellular nuclei, and cytoplasmic "peri-nuclear halo." As dying koilocytes shed, the virus particles are eliminated. ⁽¹⁴⁾

It could take up to 20 years after a high risk human papilloma virus (HR HPV) infection for malignant alterations to manifest. For cells to undergo malignant transformation, HPV infection must continue. Typically, the host genome has integrated HPV DNA. The E2 region is disturbed when cells with high risk HPV DNA integrate into them. ⁽¹⁴⁾

The virus is able to maintain cell proliferation in highly differentiated suprabasal regions, which permits viral genome amplification, by jointly targeting various cellular pathways involved in the regulation of cell cycle control and apoptosis. ⁽⁴⁵⁾

Figure 7: HPV life cycle to cancer development. ⁽⁴⁶⁾

These cause a loss of the expected downregulation, which causes the oncogenes E6 and E7 to be upregulated. Out of all the HPV proteins, E6 and E7 are the ones most closely linked to cancers through the removal of the tumour suppressor's p53 and RB, which causes genomic instability and anti-apoptosis. The high risk HPV E7 proteins target and degrade RB1, whereas E6 proteins target TP53 and promote telomerase (TERT). When p53 targeted apoptotic activity of damaged DNA cell lost causing accumulation of damaged DNA in cells. When activity of RB gene keeps regulation of E2F (elongation factor) causing controlled cellular proliferation. When activity of RB gene lost there is uncontrolled cellular proliferation. (46)

Figure 8: Progression from a normal cervix to invasive squamous cell carcinoma mediated by HPV. (49)

These gene products can alter the cellular milieu in which a cell replicates and regularly disrupt cell growth 46. When P53 is bound by the E6 proteins, ligase-mediated P53 degradation renders the tumour-suppressive functions of P53 useless 38. Increased cellular proliferation and genomic instability are the outcomes of E6 and E7 gene products capacity to interfere with the cellular P53 and PRB protein functions.

Cells eventually develop mutations and damaged DNA, which can result in the development of fully developed malignant cells . The methylation of viral DNA, telomere activations, humoral, and immunogenic factors, in addition to the role played by the E6, E7 proteins, all contribute to cellular transformation.⁽¹⁴⁾

According to the similarity of their DNA sequences, more than 200 different HPV infection types have been identified, but only 85 of them have been thoroughly studied. Depending on their connection to precancerous lesions and cancer, they are classified as high risk or low risk. The functional difference found in the E6 and E7 proteins of the two groups 46 accounts for the variation in their ability to trigger malignant transformation. The HPV type at high risk has the ability to cause cancer. Serotypes 16, 18, 31, 33, 34, 35, 39, 41, 52, 56, 58, 66, 68 are included in this group. ⁽¹⁴⁾

Low risk HPV usually causes the development of low grade precancerous lesions and has less carcinogenic potential. These are groupings 6, 11, 42, 43, and 44. The low risk HPVs seem to be able to integrate into the host genome, however serotypes 6, 11, may occasionally cause chromosomal instability, leading to an accumulation of mutational events, which may then fully change into malignant cells. ⁽¹⁴⁾

Figure 9: Genome Structure of Human Papillomavirus (HPV).

Image Source: [Margaret A. Stanley 2012](#). ⁽⁴⁰⁾

Although many HPV infections are asymptomatic, lesions are frequently the outcome of symptomatic HPV infections. Each HPV serotype affects particular body regions and causes a different kind of lesion. ⁽¹⁴⁾

For instance, HPV types 1 and 2 are linked to hand warts, whereas HPV types 6, 11, 16, 18, 31, 33, 35, 39, 45 are linked to the most prevalent ano-genital infections.

Genital warts are abnormal growths or lumps in the genital areas that are proliferative foci of epithelial keratinocytes infected with HPV. This is one of the most frequently observed clinically diagnosed diseases caused by genital HPV, which is frequently discovered in the vulva, cervix, vagina, and anus. They are highly contagious, and even in couples utilising the barrier method of contraception, perineal transmission can happen. ⁽¹⁵⁾

Overcoming host immune resistance, potential integration of HPV DNA into the host genome, and accumulation of further mutations inside the infected host cell are all steps that must be taken between the initial infection and the onset of cancer. However, in order to promote neoplastic alterations, HPV must remain persistent within the host epithelial cells. The conventional wisdom has been

that following the initial HPV infection, this process takes years, if not decades, to take place. According to certain studies, these alterations might occur more swiftly than previously believed.⁽¹⁶⁾

“It is inexpensive and non-invasive, and it may be carried out in a primary health centre. More importantly, VIA offers immediate results, and individuals who qualify for treatment can undergo cryotherapy treatment for precancerous lesions the same day and in the same medical centre. This "see and treat" approach makes sure that therapy is followed right away after a diagnosis.”⁽²⁰⁾

Public health systems can provide VIA cervical cancer screening in more rural (and less equipped) healthcare settings and achieve higher coverage due to the need for less training of workers, infrastructure, and equipment. Women can be screened and treated in the same visit thanks to the VIA's quick results sharing capabilities between healthcare professionals and their patients. This makes it possible to provide immediate follow-up care, which lowers the number of women who might otherwise be overlooked for up. For instance, in a "screen and treat" experiment in Peru, 44% of women who were lost to treatment using a multi-visit strategy were lost, while just 9% of women who tested positive failed to receive treatment in the single-visit approach.⁽²¹⁾

Although some researchers utilise an indeterminate or inconclusive category, negative and positive categories based on the absence or presence of acetowhite lesions and clinical symptoms of invasive malignancy are the most typical ways to present the results of the VIA test. ⁽²²⁾ One minute after the application of 3-5% acetic acid, a positive test is often based on the detection of well-defined, densely opaque acetowhite lesions in the transformation zone closer to the squamocolumnar junction. The following criteria have been used to determine whether a test is positive: absence of acetowhite lesions, faint, poorly defined, translucent acetowhite lesions, endocervical polyps, Nabothian cysts, dot-like aceto white lesions, acetowhite lesions far from the transformation zone, and a prominent squamocolumnar junction. ⁽²²⁾

However, there are some differences across the research groups in terms of these categories and the criteria used to identify them. Near some of the reported and continuing research, the acetowhite lesion's colour intensity (pale or dull white) and placement (in, close to, or far away from the squamocolumnar junction/transformation zone) have had a significant role in determining the test's outcome. ⁽²²⁾

Depending on the degree of whiteness, attempts have been made to categorise good outcomes as "faintly" or "strongly" positive. However, the accuracy of the

test was hardly affected by this categorisation. In the majority of published and continuing research, the test-positive rate ranges from 10 to 35%.^(23, 24)

Since VIA is a screening test that is fully dependent on the provider, this difference is not unusual. One of the reporting schemes employed classifications like "Normal," "Atypical," "Abnormal," and "Cervical cancer," where the abnormal category matched the positive classification in other reporting methods. When no obvious acetowhite lesions or slightly dubious lesions are visible, or when the cervix cannot be properly diagnosed, an uncertain category has also been utilised. Different definitions and systems may have made it more difficult to compare the findings from varying research due to misclassification, observer variation, and different thresholds for referral. For reporting VIA findings, uniformly reproducible categories are becoming increasingly important.⁽²⁵⁾

There is growing agreement that the detection of extensive acetowhite lesions with distinct borders in the transformation zone, near the squamo - columnar junction, indicates a successful VIA test.⁽²⁵⁾

Cryotherapy has been effectively combined with visual inspection with acetic acid (VIA), a reasonably easy and affordable procedure for treating cervical lesions that can be carried out by primary care physicians and mid-level practitioners. In comparison to other treatment techniques including cone biopsy, loop electrosurgical excision procedure (LEEP), and loop excision of the transformation zone (LETZ), cryotherapy is more effective at treating precancerous lesions and simpler to use. ^(26, 27)

It also has additional benefits, such as being economical, not requiring sophisticated equipment (albeit energy is required), and being doable by less specialised staff, allowing it to be used in a Primary Health-Care (PHC) context. ⁽²⁸⁾

An overall decrease in morbidity and death from cervix cancer is linked to secondary prevention of cervical cancer through the detection and treatment of precancerous lesions of the cervix. ^(29, 30)

The primary issue with the VIA test is its low specificity (high false-positive rate), which necessitates the recall of numerous participants for colposcopy.

According to a prior study, the frequency of referral following VIA was shown to range between 3.1 and 38.7%.⁽³¹⁾

Due to high incidence of co-infections (chronic inflammation in the lower vaginal tract) in HIV-positive women, specificity is substantially lower.⁽³²⁾

It is recommended that good provider training and ongoing quality assurance be implemented because VIA is prone to subjectivity in order to reduce high false positive rates anxiety, and unneeded treatment.^(30, 33)

PREDISPOSING RISK FACTORS

There are many characteristics and risk factors that predispose to cervical cancer

- Average age 35-45 years
- HPV Persistent infection 16, 18, 31, 33
- Early intercourse before 18 years
- Multiple sexual partners
- Delivery of 1st baby before the age of 20 years

- Multiparity
- Poor birth spacing
- Poor personal hygiene
- Poor socioeconomic status
- Smoking and drug abuse
- Immuno-supressed individual

SCREENING

“The screening mainly starts in individual with active sexual life. Mainly at the age of 21 years with conventional method (Pap smear) every 3 years. After 30 years of age HPV DNA testing can be used every 5 years. After age of 30 both HPV DNA testing and Pap smear can be used for screening every 5 years till 65 years of age if tests are negative. When both test (HPV DNA testing, Pap smear) when used together can be known as Co-testing. Which increases sensitivity and specificity of the screening tests.”

“In women with age above 65 who has never screened should undergo screening. In immunocompromised women (HIV-AIDS) should undergo screening

annually. Screening in hysterectomised women not required unless cervix left behind.”

The cervical cancer primarily caused by infection with certain types of human papillomavirus. So mainly screening targeted on detecting HPV infection or cervical (microscopic cell level) changes.

In many instances, effective screening and immunisation against the most cancer-causing HPV infection types were helpful.

It appears that an immunocompetent host needsto be exposed to various cervical cancer risk factors or carcinogenic events over a long period of time before a woman develops invasive cervical cancer, rather than just HPV infection alone. ⁽⁸⁾

Targets for each of the three pillars of a global strategy to hasten cervical cancer eradication include the following for 2030 ⁽⁹⁾

- a. 90% of eligible girls have had the human papillomavirus (HPV) vaccine.
- b. 70% have undergone a high-performance test for screening.
- c. 90% have had a cervical lesion treated as necessary.

The WHO suggests that women in general begin routine cervical cancer screening at the age of 30. The WHO recommends that women with HIV begin routine cervical cancer screening at the age of 25.

Women aged 30-49 should be given priority when being screened among all females. Women in the 50-65 age range who have never been screened should be given priority when technologies are available to manage them.

Infections with HPV affected 43 million people in 2018, many of whom were in their late teens and early 20s. There are numerous varieties of HPV. Some forms, such as genital warts and cancer, can lead to health issues. However, there are immunizations that can prevent these medical issues from occurring.

WHO advises utilising HPV DNA detection as the primary screening test rather than VIA or cytology in screening and treatment approaches for the general population of women and women living with HIV.

When utilising VIA or cytology as the primary screening test, the WHO recommends a regular screening interval of every three years among both the

general population of women and women living with HIV in areas where HPV DNA testing is not yet operational. ⁽⁹⁾

The greater reductions in cervical cancer and deaths that are likely with HPV DNA detection as compared to using VIA or cytology as a primary screening test were given a higher value, leading to a strong recommendation for using it as a primary screening test when part of a screen-and-treat approach or a screen, triage , and treat approach.

Where it is not currently available, quality controlled, and assured, offering cytology or colposcopy would be a hurdle when choosing a triage test. However, if the HPV DNA primary screening test also revealed information about the genotype of HPV 16/18. HPV DNA testing crucial for a self-sampling technique because there wouldn't be a need to perform a separate test. Self-sampling HPV DNA testing also has the potential to lower gender, socioeconomic, and cultural screening barriers, which is expected to improve fairness.

Screen-and-treat approaches ⁽⁹⁾:

1. Visual inspection with acetic acid (VIA) as the primary screening test, followed by treatment.
2. HPV DNA (self or clinician collected) as the primary screening test, followed by treatment.

Screen, triage and treat approaches:

3. Cytology as the primary screening test, followed by colposcopy triage, followed by treatment.
4. HPV DNA as the primary screening test, followed by HPV16/18 triage (when already part of the HPV test), followed by treatment, and using VIA triage for those who screen negative for HPV 16/18.
5. HPV DNA as the primary screening-test, followed by VIA triage, followed by treatment.
6. High-risk HPV DNA as the primary screening test, followed by colposcopy triage, followed by treatment.
7. HPV DNA as the primary screening test, followed by cytology triage, followed by colposcopy and treatment.

Screening methods available are ⁽⁹⁾:

Molecular	Cytologic	Visual inspection
<p>Nucleic acid amplification tests (NAAT)^a » high-risk HPV DNA/NAAT » mRNA</p> <p>DNA methylation^b</p> <p>Protein biomarker's^b » HPV antibodies » oncoproteins</p>	<p>Conventional Pap smear</p> <p>Liquid-based cytology (LBC)^a</p> <p>Dual staining to identify p16 and Ki-67^a</p>	<p>Visual inspection with Acetic acid or with Lugols iodine(VIA/VILI)^a » naked eye » magnified by colposcope or camera</p> <p>Automated visual Evaluation of digital images^b</p>

a. Current tests.

b. Tests under evaluation (future tests).

HPV test :

Several in vitro diagnostic medical tools are utilised for the nucleic acid amplification test known as the risk HPV DNA test (NAAT). The most prevalent oncogenic genotypes, HPV types 16 and 18, have been particularly detected by HPV NAAT, which identifies the women who are most at risk of getting cervical cancer.

This is based on the finding of high-risk HPV DNA from these kinds in vaginal and/or cervical samples ; most laboratory tests can identify up to 15 HPV types. HPV tests have the ability to either detect distinct HPV types via genotyping capacity or can detect high-risk HPV genotypes in bulk without differentiating between the particular types.

With so many HPV tests available in a variety of forms, choosing the right test type is crucial for accurate prediction. Supports utilising HPV DNA detection as the primary screening test for women living with HIV at a regular screening interval of every 3 to 5 years. When utilising HPV DNA detection as the primary screening test among the general population of women, the WHO recommends a routine screening interval of every 5 to 10 years.

Figure 10 : HPV DNA testing (PCR).

Visual inspection with acetic acid (VIA):

Utilizing a 3-5% acetic acid solution to temporarily create what is described as a "acetowhite lesion," VIA is a direct visual examination of the cervix. In the case of CIN2/3 and aggressive cancer, this develops after one minute and can linger for three to five minutes. Women whose transition zone is visible should utilise VIA (typically in those younger than 50 years).⁽⁹⁾

However, VIA is a more affordable and practical technique for screening women in underdeveloped nations. High subjective variability in VIA.⁽⁹⁾

Figure 11: VIA negative⁽¹²⁾

Figure 12: VIA positive⁽¹²⁾

This is due to the fact that after menopause, the transformation zone, which is where the majority of pre-cancer lesions are found, frequently recedes into the endocervical canal and is therefore not completely visible. With VIA programmes, it is challenging to create and sustain quality assurance. Because of this, VIA testing's sensitivity and specificity might vary greatly.

VIA-based program requires quality assurance (QA) to assure successful implementation. Digital imaging of VIA (D-VIA) is an adjunctive procedure to improve diagnosis performance. D-VIA using Smartphone is a low-cost and easy-to-use method for QA. Or along with colposcopy can be used to increase the quality assurance.

Figure13: PRIMARY VIA SCREENING (SCREEN-AND TREAT APPROACH)
VIA testing ⁽⁹⁾

- a. Ablative treatment includes cryotherapy and thermal ablation.
- b. Cold knife conization (CKC) if LLETZ not available.
- c. LLETZ and LEEP (loop electrosurgical excision procedure) indicate the same procedure.
- d. Histology may not be available in certain settings; women should be advised to attend follow-up after 1 year or to report earlier, if they have any of the symptoms of cervical cancer.

(AIS: adenocarcinoma in situ; CIN: cervical intraepithelial neoplasia; LLETZ: large-loop excision of the transformation zone; VIA: visual inspection with acetic acid).

VILI

“The Schiller's test, also known as visual inspection with Lugol's iodine (VILI), substitutes Lugol's iodine for acetic acid. Performing a vaginal speculum examination, in which the cervix is treated with Lugol's iodine solution. Observing the cervix with the unaided eye to spot any changes in colour. Determining whether a test result for potential cancer or precancerous lesions is positive or negative.”⁽⁴⁸⁾

“Basis of VILI the glycogen-containing squamous cells tint mahogany brown when lugol's iodine is applied, demonstrating the uptake of iodine. The columnar epithelium, however, does not contain glycogen, does not absorb iodine, and does not get coloured. Cancer that has spread and aberrant cell growth do not absorb iodine and remain mustard yellow.” (48)

“VILI sensitivity is 87.2% and its specificity is 84.7%. Management of VILI positive cases mainly biopsy or carry out screen and treat (treatment like cryotherapy). Advantages are low cost, easily done in low setup, results available immediately. Limitations are in a single-visit method, moderate specificity may lead to over-referral and over-treatment. When applied to post-menopausal women, it is less accurate.” (48)

Figure 14: VILI negative.

The squamous epithelium turns brown and columnar epithelium does not change colour.

Figure 15: VILI positive
Well-defined, bright
yellow iodine non uptake
areas touching the
squamo-columnar
junction (SCJ).

Cytology

The Papanicolaou (Pap) test, often known as a liquid-based smear test, determines whether the cervix's cells are abnormal. Speculum examination is used to collect cells, which are then either placed directly onto a slide to which a fixative is applied (traditional cytology) or placed in a bottle with a liquid storage media (liquid-based cytology).⁽⁹⁾

There may be pre-cancer changes in the cervix if abnormal cervical cells that test as “atypical squamous cells of unknown significance (ASCUS), low grade to high grade” are found.⁽⁹⁾

ASCUS was utilised as the cut-off for an abnormal test requiring additional analysis when high-risk HPV DNA was present. A woman may need to have her cervix checked, undergo additional testing (such as an HPV DNA test), or undergo ablative or excisional treatment to have the pre-cancer lesion removed if a cytology test results in a positive result. ⁽⁹⁾

The most widely used cervical screening technique is the papanicolaou smear (Pap smear). Numerous studies demonstrate high specificity of over 92% ⁽¹⁷⁾ and sensitivity of over 70% or more. ^(18, 19)

Sadly, cervical cytology has considerably decreased the incidence of cervical cancer in wealthy nations; it is less well established in nations with limited resources.

Figure 16: Pap smear. The cytologic features of normal squamous epithelial cells can be seen at the center top and bottom, with orange to pale blue plate-like squamous cells that have small pyknotic nuclei. The dysplastic cells in the center extending to upper right are smaller overall with darker, more irregular nuclei.

Bethesda system

The Bethesda system provides a framework for consistent interlaboratory terminology for the reporting of cervicovaginal cytology specimen.

- Interpretation : Epithelial cell abnormalities
 - Squamous cell
 - Atypical squamous cells
 - Of undetermined significance (ASC-US)
 - Cannot exclude HSIL (ASC-H)
 - Low grade squamous intraepithelial lesion (LSIL) (Synonyms: mild dysplasia / CIN I)
 - High grade squamous intraepithelial lesion (HSIL) (Synonyms: moderate dysplasia, severe dysplasia, CIN2, CIN3)
 - With features suspicious for invasion (if invasion suspected)
 - Squamous cell carcinoma

Figure 17: showing LSIL, HSIL

Atypical squamous cells of undetermined significance (ASC-US): This is the most common abnormal Pap test finding. HPV test is done. If positive advised to

- Return for a repeat HPV test or HPV/Pap co-test in 1 or 3 years.
- Have a colposcopy and biopsy.
- Receive treatment (ablation or excision of abnormal cells).

Low-grade squamous intraepithelial lesions (LSIL): There are low-grade changes that are usually caused by an HPV infection. HPV testing done. If positive proceed

- Return for a repeat HPV test or HPV/Pap co-test in 1 or 3 years.
- Have a colposcopy and biopsy.
- Receive treatment (ablation or excision of abnormal cells).

Atypical squamous cells, cannot exclude high-grade squamous intraepithelial lesion (ASC-H): colposcopy is done. And treated accordingly.

High-grade squamous intraepithelial lesions (HSIL): There are moderately or severely abnormal cervical cells that could become cancer in the future if not treated (ablation or excision of abnormal cells).

Cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN)

“Cervical intraepithelial neoplasia results from HPV infection within cervical cells. The degree of dysplasia is determined by the percentage of cervical epithelium that contains dysplastic cells by histopathological examination. When compared to the more serious CIN-2 and CIN-3 (high-grade), which proceed to involve the full thickness of the epithelium, CIN-1 (low-grade) only affects the lower third or less of the epithelium. When dysplasia penetrates the basement membrane, it develops into cancer.”⁽⁵⁰⁾

“After a year, about 60% of CIN-1 will revert back to normal. Despite the fact that the typical period for advancement is still a number of years, women with CIN-2 and CIN-3 are at a significant risk of having invasive cancer. Women with CIN-2/3 should therefore get treatment.”⁽⁵⁰⁾

“Treatment for CIN-1 is to undergo observation and co-testing repeated in 1 year. If CIN-1 is persistent after 2 years or progresses within that time, treatment is the recommendation. CIN -2 or higher requires treatment, usual treatment is via ablation or excision of abnormal cells. Ablation of abnormal cells includes cryosurgery or laser ablation (CO2 laser). Excisional procedures for the treatment of CIN include LEEP, cold knife conization, and laser conization. During

pregnancy, treatment is postponed until after delivery unless colposcopic surveillance during pregnancy reveals progression to invasive cervical cancer.”⁽⁵⁰⁾

“After receiving treatment for CIN-2 or above, women should get their Pap smear and get HPV testing 12 and 24 months later. The treatment is regarded as 70 to 80% successful even when an excised specimen has positive endocervical margins. The recommended course of treatment when margins are positive is repeat cytology testing in 4-6 months along with an endocervical curettage. One approach for the treatment of chronic or recurrent CIN-2 or 3 is a second excisional surgery. In some cases, patients will decide to have a hysterectomy, which is also suitable for CIN that persists.”⁽⁵⁰⁾

Liquid Based Cytology

“LBC, samples are obtained in liquid vials, and the lab prepares the slide semi-automatically. Potential benefits of LBC include a decrease in the quantity of subpar slides, increased test sensitivity, and increased smear reading efficiency.”

“The use of Human Papilloma Virus (HPV) testing in the management of women with mild or borderline smear results in addition to studying LBC can be done in same sample. More than 95% of female cervical cancer patients have HPV infection. Women who test negative for this virus could potentially be kept out of needless preventative therapy at colposcopy clinics.”⁽⁵³⁾

“Liquid based cytology has sensitivity of 55.3%, specificity of 77.7%. Positive cytology is managed as positive Pap smear results.”⁽⁵³⁾

Colposcopy

Used largely in conjunction with screening instruments for detecting, diagnosing, and treating cervical pre-cancer lesions, a colposcope is a low-magnification, light-illuminated visualisation device. It enables the examiner to see the cervix's and the ano-genital regions' epithelial tissues. The type of transformation zone and the grade of probable epithelial abnormalities are helpful for assessing cervical pre-cancer. As a screening tool, it is hardly frequently utilised. After a primary positive screening test, a colposcopy may be utilised to determine whether ablative or excisional therapy is necessary. Colposcopy also makes biopsy and excisional treatment easier and more effective. To become proficient in colposcopy, one needs training and supervision.

Figure 18: Five colposcopic images (Normal, CIN1, CIN2, CIN3 and Cancer)⁽⁵¹⁾

Figure 19: Precancerous Colposcopic patterns. (a) Network capillaries, (b) hairpin capillaries, (c) punctation capillaries, (d) mosaic capillaries and (e and f) atypical capillaries. ⁽⁵²⁾

Treatment consideration in positive screening test

Women who test positive are treated without a histology diagnosis under a screen-and-treat strategy.

The cervix's transformation zone is intended to be destroyed or removed, as well as any cervix regions that have been detected as abnormal during screening.

To lower the chance of follow-up loss, it is best to treat as soon as feasible within six months. Deferring till after pregnancy is a healthy habit, nonetheless, for pregnant women.

The types of treatments include ablative (removing aberrant tissue surgically using large loop excision of the transformation zone-LLETZ or Conisation of the **cervix** or cold knife cone CKC) and excisional (freezing or heating abnormal tissue to cause thermal coagulation).

Treatments that are ablative do not produce a tissue sample for histological analysis .

METHODS AND METHEDODOLOGY

AIMS OF THE STUDY

The purpose of study is to study the cervical histopathologies in aceto-white areas as a result of VIA test of the cervix when acetic acid applied.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

To study the spectrum and proportion of cervical histopathologies in aceto-white areas of the cervix.

METHODOLOGY

This is a cross-sectional study. The women who fulfil the inclusion criteria will be studied. Consents will be taken once the patient is willing for this study.

In lithotomy position per speculum examination is done. Sterile Cusco's self-retaining vaginal speculum is inserted and cervix is inspected by naked eye.

Acetic acid 3-5% is applied to the cervical area and observed for aceto-white lesions after 1 minute .From these, cervical biopsy is taken from these

areas and suspicious lesions and sent to a pathologist for histopathology evaluation. These histopathological diagnosis correlated with VIA findings.

The proportion of cervical pathologies will be seen in this study in low resource settings.

SOURCE OF DATA

The study will be conducted at B.L.D.E (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY) SHRI B.M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH CENTRE. In this study, the women are selected as per the inclusion criteria and exclusion criteria and women visiting Obstetrics and Gynaecology outpatient department and women underwent screening under screening programs organised by OBG department.

DURATION OF STUDY

Study period from January 2021 to May 2022.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- The sexually active women in the age group of 30-49 years.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Menopause
- Post hysterectomy
- Known HIV and HbsAg positive
- Pregnancy

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. Carol. et al. (2008) conducted a study on 502 rural women, and they were screened for cervical cancer by VIA and colposcopy as a screening technique. The presence of cervicitis assessed by grading the amount of inflammation on cervical biopsy. They found Data from 495 women found to be free from neoplasia. 74% women were having cervicitis. The women with cervicitis were twice as likely to have positive VIA results. The presence of the cervicitis may influence the accuracy of results from VIA and colposcopy. This observation has particular importance in low resource settings where commonly used screening tool is VIA. ⁽¹⁾

2. Surendra S. Shastri et al. (2005) in this study multiple screening methods used such as Cytology, HPV testing, VIA, VIA under magnification and visual inspection with Lugol's iodine (VILI) on 4039 women who were included according to inclusion criteria. Adding multiple screening tests gave increased sensitivity but decreased specificity. Differences in sensitivity were not significant in this study. Cytology was the best single screening test with the best balance of specificity and sensitivity. The sensitivity of cytology and Human papillomavirus testing increased by using a visual test such as VIA as these are more promising in a low resource setting. ⁽³⁵⁾

3. Atef M Darwish et al. (2013) done a study on 3500 women by unaided naked eye examination (UNEE) on non-pregnant women aged between 25 and 55 years. The cervix is examined under good source of light to notice any cervical lesion. Pap smear and endo-cervical sample were taken. The patient with abnormal Pap and visible cervical lesion by UNEE scheduled for colposcopy. They found 9 cases with pre-invasive cervical lesions (cervical intraepithelial neoplasia [CIN] I-III). 6 invasive cervical lesions. Hence the sensitivity of UNEE better than Pap smear but less than colposcopy. But specificity is less than Pap smear and more than colposcopy. Hence Pap smear accessibility is limited UNEE can be performed. ⁽³⁴⁾

4. Ashish Bhattacharyya et al. (2015) a study done on 300 women aged 18 to 60 years, Pap smear and VIA are done in these cases, for the positive cases cervical biopsy was taken and subjected to histopathological studies, they found 22 cytology positive results and 19 CIN and carcinoma cervix out of 52 VIA positive cases. VIA found to be 89% sensitive, and specificity was 87%. Lower specificity of VIA when compared to Pap smear, might be due to inflammation, immature metaplasia, or latent human papillomavirus (HPV). ⁽³⁶⁾

5. Usha Poli et al. (2015) a study carried out in a rural area with a large group of women. Prior health education was conducted by trained female health workers among the women. Eligible women in the age group selected and a single round

of VIA testing done. Total of 18869 women was screened with positive results of 10.75%.and further evaluation done, such as cervical biopsy. After the biopsy results, women underwent cryotherapies and hysterectomy. VIA is an important implication for effective service in screening. ⁽³⁷⁾

RESULT

Women visited Obstetrics and Gynaecology outpatient department and women attended screening programs organised by Obstetrics and Gynaecology department participated in this study. 880 women enrolled in the study after fulfilling criteria for inclusion, ruling out exclusion criteria.

The results are as follows.

DISTRIBUTION OF AGE OF STUDY PARTICIPANT

Table 1: Age distribution of study participant.

Age(Years)	Number of Women	%
< 35	307	34.9
35 - 39	231	26.3
40 - 44	149	16.9
45+	193	21.9
Total	880	100.0

Figure 20: Age distribution of study participant.

The age ranged from 30 to 49 years of women. The mean age of study population was 37.72 ± 6.149 . As depicted here, majority of the women belonged to 30 to < 35 years of age of study participant i.e. 307 (35%), least among women belonged to 40-44 years of age group i.e. 17% (149 study participant). As age of women increases ignorance towards her own health increases due to emotional and psycho-social aspects of her life.

Table 2. DISTRIBUTION OF MARRIED LIFE IN STUDY PARTICIPANT

MARRIED LIFE (in years)	Frequency	Percent
< 10	95	10.8
10 – 19	478	54.3
20 – 29	280	31.8
30+	27	3.1
Total	880	100.0

Figure 21: Graph depicting married life distribution of study participant.

The married life of study participants was from 1 year to 30 years. The mean married life of study population was years 16.62 ± 6.526 (standard deviation).

Among them the maximum is 10-14 years of married life of study participant constituted 478 women (54.3%).

Table 3. DISTRIBUTION OF PARITY STATUS IN STUDY PARTICIPANT

Para	Number of women	%
0	22	2.5
1	67	7.6
2	415	47.2
3	321	36.5
4	37	4.2
5	13	1.5
6	4	0.5
8	1	0.1
Total	880	100.0

Figure 22: Graph depicting distribution of parity status in study participant.

Women in this study participant has parity of range 0- 8. Major women had parity of 2 constituting 47.2% (415). Least parity of women was 8 constituted 0.1 % (1 of study participants).

Table 4. DISTRIBUTION OF LIVING CHILDREN IN STUDY PARTICIPANT

Living Children	Number of women	%
0	22	2.5
1	73	8.3
2	416	47.3
3	309	35.1
4	45	5.1
5	13	1.5
6	1	0.1
8	1	0.1
Total	880	100.0

Figure 23: Graph depicting distribution of living issue in study participant

Women in this study has living children range 0-8 children. Women with 2 as maximum children constituting 47.3% (416 study participants with 2 children).

Least women with of number 6, 8 children by 1, 1, each study participant.

Table 5. DISTRIBUTION OF PAST HISTORY IN STUDY PARTICIPANT

Past History	Number of Women	%
Significant	9	0.9
Nothing significant	871	99.1
Total	880	100.0

Figure 24: Graph depicting distribution of past medical history in study participant.

This table depicts 98.9 % of women with no past history. Only 11 participants had significant past medical history such as known case of Diabetes mellitus, Hypertension, Hypothyroidism, Underwent appendectomy etc.

Table 6. DISTRIBUTION OF CERVIX AND VAGINA HEALTHY IN STUDY PARTICIPANT.

Cervix and Vagina Healthy	Number of Women	%	VIA POSITIVE
NO	188	21.3	7
YES	692	78.6	5
Total	880	100.0	12

Figure 25: Graph depicting distribution of cervix and vagina healthy in study participant.

Table depicting 707 (80.3%) women in our study group has healthy Cervix and Vagina. 173 study participant has either cervical erosion, cervical hypertrophy, vaginitis, white discharge which constitutes 19.7% of study participant. VIA positive was associated with unhealthy cervix and vagina.

Table 7. DISTRIBUTION OF CERVICAL EROSION IN STUDY PARTICIPANT.

Cervical Erosion	Number of Women	%	VIA POSITIVE
NO	698	79.3	6
YES	182	20.7	6
Total	880	100.0	12

Figure 26: Graph depicting distribution of cervical erosion in study participants.

Table depicting 698 (79.3%) women in our study group has healthy Cervix. 182 study participants has cervical erosion, compromising 20.7% of study participants. VIA positive was associated with cervical erosion.

Table 8. DISTRIBUTION OF CERVICAL HYPERTROPHY IN STUDY PARTICIPANT.

Cervical Hypertrophy	Number of Women	%	VIA POSITIVE
NO	858	97.5	8
YES	22	2.5	4
Total	880	100.0	12

Figure 27: Graph depicting distribution of cervical hypertrophy in study participants.

Table depicting 858 (97.5%) women in our study group has healthy Cervix. 22 study participant has cervical hypertrophy, comprising 2.5% of study participant. VIA positive was associated with cervical hypertrophy.

Table 9: DISTRIBUTION OF VAGINITIS IN STUDY PARTICIPANT

Vaginitis	Number of Women	%	VIA POSITIVE
NO	838	95.2	12
YES	42	4.8	0
Total	880	100.0	12

Figure 28: Graph depicting distribution of vaginitis in study participant.

Table depicting 838 (95.2%) women in our study group has healthy Vagina. 42 study participant has vaginitis, compromising 4.8% of study participant. VIA positive was not associated with vaginitis.

Table 10. DISTRIBUTION OF WHITE DISCHARGE IN STUDY**PARTICIPANT**

White Discharge	Number of Women	%	VIA POSITIVE
NO	709	80.6	9
PRESENT	171	19.5	3
Total	880	100.0	12

Figure 29: Graph depicting distribution of white discharge in study participants.

Table depicting 709 (80.6%) women in our study group has no white discharge. 171 study participants has white discharge on examination, comprising 19.5% of study participants. VIA positive was associated with white discharge.

Table 11. DISTRIBUTION OF VIA IN STUDY PARTICIPANT

VIA	Number of Women	%
NEGATIVE	806	91.6
POSITIVE	74	8.4
Total	880	100.0

Figure 30: Graph depicting distribution of white discharge in study participant.

In 880 total study participants with positive VIA was 74 study participants constituting prevalence of VIA is 8.4%. 806 has negative VIA results in study participants constituting 91.6 %.

Table 12. DISTRIBUTION OF BIOPSY RESULTS IN STUDY PARTICIPANT

Biopsy Results (n-880)	Number of women	%
NO BIOPSY TAKEN	806	91.7
CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS	24	2.7
CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA WITH NABOTHIAN CYST	14	1.6
CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA	13	1.5
CHRONIC CERVICITIS	5	0.6
CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH PAPILLARY ENDOCERVICITIS	1	0.1
PAPILLARY ENDOCERVICITIS	3	0.4
PAPILLARY ENDOCERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA	1	0.1
NO SPECIFIC PATHOLOGY	4	0.5
NORMAL STUDY	1	0.1
CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH MILD DYSPLASIA	4	0.5
CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SEVERE DYSPLASIA	1	0.1
WELL DIFFERENTIATED SQUAMOUS CELL CARCINOMA	1	0.1
Total	880	100.0

74 cervical biopsy taken (VIA positive), Chronic Non Specific Cervicitis finding was highest with 24 women, constituting 2.7% of total study participant, 33.8 % of total VIA positivity. 14 study participant biopsy showed Chronic Non-Specific Cervicitis with Squamous Metaplasia with Nabothian Cyst (1.6%). 13 study participant biopsy showed Chronic Non-Specific Cervicitis With Squamous Metaplasia (1.5%). 5 study participant biopsy showed chronic cervicitis (0.6%), 1 study participant biopsy showed Chronic Non Specific Cervicitis With Papillary Endocervicitis, 3 study participant biopsy showed Papillary Endocervicitis, 1 study participant biopsy showed Papillary Endocervicitis With Squamous Metaplasia.

4 study participant biopsy showed no specific pathology, 1 study participant biopsy showed normal study.

4 study participant biopsy showed Chronic Non-Specific Cervicitis with MILD DYSPLASIA (LSIL), 1 Study Participant Biopsy Showed Chronic Non-Specific Cervicitis with Severe DYSPLASIA (HSIL), 1 study participant biopsy showed WELL DIFFERENTIATED SQUAMOUS CELL CARCINOMA.

Table 13. DISTRIBUTION OF BIOPSY RESULTS AMONG VIA POSITIVE IN STUDY PARTICIPANT

Biopsy Results (n-74)	Number of women	%
CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS	25	33.8
CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA WITH NABOTHIAN CYST	14	18.9
CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA	13	17.6
CHRONIC CERVICITIS	5	6.8
CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH PAPILLARY ENDOCERVICITIS	1	1.4
PAPILLARY ENDOCERVICITIS	3	4.1
PAPILLARY ENDOCERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA	1	1.4
NO SPECIFIC PATHOLOGY	4	5.4
NORMAL STUDY	1	1.4
CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH MILD DYSPLASIA	4	5.4
CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SEVERE DYSPLASIA	1	1.4
WELL DIFFERENTIATED SQUAMOUS CELL CARCINOMA	1	1.4
Total	74	100.0

Figure 31: Distribution of biopsy results among VIA positive in study participant.

46.2 % of biopsy report showed cervicitis of 74 VIA positive women, 37.9% of biopsy report showed cervicitis with squamous metaplasia. Total 84.1% of biopsy report showed chronic cervicitis of biopsy taken from aceto-white areas (VIA positive), 6.8% (4 LSIL, 1 HSIL) of biopsy report showed premalignant changes. 1.4% of biopsy report showed cervical cancer.

DISCUSSION

“VIA positivity in our study was 8.4% where 880 study participants underwent VIA with direct visual inspection. In our study VIA positivity was present in 82.4% of cervical inflammation. Similar study done by Haripriya Vedantham in a Peri-Urban Area in Andhra Pradesh, India in 2010, VIA positivity was recorded in 23.6% with cervical inflammation.”⁽⁴⁰⁾

“In our study the VIA positivity was high mainly due to cervical inflammation as compared to other studies. From this study it can be predicted, population staying in this city mainly has high prevalence of cervical inflammation has participated in this study.”

“Poor repeatability of VIA performance across large populations would be anticipated given the substantial regional variation in the frequency of cervical inflammation and the inability to pinpoint the infectious agent responsible.”

“The intervention study in Osmanabad, India, examined the effectiveness of HPV, cytology, and VIA tests for cervical cancer. However, the final assessment found that VIA (or Pap smear) screening was unsuccessful in lowering the incidence of advanced cervical cancer and related mortality⁽⁴¹⁾. On the other

hand, HPV screening significantly decreased the prevalence of advanced cervical malignancies and the related mortality.”⁽⁴⁰⁾

“It is most likely that VIA's (and cytology's) poor performance in the final analysis was caused by their poorer sensitivity in detecting women with cervical cancer or its precursors, and that the original judgement that VIA and the HPV assay had equal sensitivity was inaccurate. This body of research thus verifies the subjective VIA test's high degree of diagnostic accuracy variability, which is not significantly decreased even when employing standard protocols and training programmes.”⁽⁴⁰⁾

“In our study positivity, sensitivity, specificity cannot be predicted. As all VIA positive study participant underwent biopsy, which is negative. If we follow “screen and triage”, women would have over treated unnecessarily.”

“In our study women with age group 30-49 have undergone VIA screening. As no abnormal was found. Screening should be done in all married women or sexually active women to rule out cervical lesions and treated as earliest possible. Women with more than 50 years and menopausal women should be encouraged to undergo screening procedure and should be educated regarding same, as most women in that age group least vaccinated.”

“VIA screening should be combined with other effective screening methods like VILI, Colposcopy, HPV DNA testing, biopsy, Cytological.”

“This study is a cross-sectional study, studied the spectrum and proportion of cervical histopathologies in aceto-white areas of the cervix when acetic acid is applied to cervix and examined by naked eye.”

“Our study included 880 study participants of age group between 30-49 years. The mean age of study population was 37.49 ± 6.038 . Likewise the study conducted in Sankaranarayanan et al, to analyse the efficacy of the visual acetic acid test conducted by the doctor and paramedical worker. This constituted the major age group of 25-65 years.”

“Similar studies carried out in various places included age group mainly women from 20s and menopausal women (25- 85 years). In our study no menopausal women were included i.e above 50 years of age women were excluded.”

“The married life of study participant’s was 1- 30 years, 88.7% belonged to more than 10 years of married life, and 36.3% study population completed more than 20 years of married life. Michelle S. Longworth et.al studied pathogenesis of HPV infection and association into cervical cancer, basal cells that are infected

with virus can endure for several decades or until the immune system gets rid of the virus. ⁽¹⁴⁾ As HPV virus is associated with 99% of cervical cancer.” ⁽⁴⁶⁾

“Most of the women in our study fell under para 2 and 3, which are common in developing nations like India. They are often sterilised permanently as a form of contraceptive method.”

“As each screening test has its own sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value. As screening test should be feasible, cheap applied to healthy volunteers. Still HPV DNA tests are not available due to its cost and the greatest limitations of HPV testing were the need for expensive laboratory infrastructure and the 4-7 h time to process the test. Available HPV tests are ability to use methods for signal amplification to determine the presence of viral indicators, such as the Digene Hybrid Capture® II test or nucleic acid amplification using the polymerase chain reaction.” ⁽⁴²⁾

“The biggest benefit of HPV-based testing is evident in that it enables patient-performed sample collection, eliminating the need for infrastructure and trained employees to conduct a pelvic examination. In comparison to cytology, the requirements for a high-quality sample are less stringent with HPV testing.” ⁽⁴²⁾

“The accuracy of VIA results may be impacted by the presence of cervicitis. This finding may be especially significant in low-resource countries where cervical cancer screenings are more frequently conducted using visual inspection techniques. The incidence of cervical pre malignancy and malignancy lesions was 6.7% and 1.37% in the population being studied with VIA respectively in our study. These findings have substantial consequences for the effective provision of services in cervical screening tests in settings with limited resources.”

“Darwish et al. In this study unaided naked eye examination of cervical cancer was compared with colposcopy and cytology. No VIA was used. UNEE (Unaided naked eye examination) Sensitivity was 80%, Specificity 91.16.”⁽³⁴⁾

Our study was similar to Carol et al, in women with cervicitis were twice as likely to have a positive VIA result as women without cervicitis. Our study, the incidence of biopsy-confirmed cervicitis was 84.1% which was similar to Carol et al, the incidence of biopsy-confirmed cervicitis was 74%.⁽¹⁾

Our study 0.6 % and 0.1 % incidence of premalignant and malignant lesion. Similar studies like Carol et al the prevalence of CIN was 1.4%. In Surendra S. Shastri et al the incidence of CIN was 4%, invasive cancer 0.7%.

TABLE 14: ACCURACY OF VISUAL INSPECTION WITH ACETIC ACID IN DETECTING CIN 2—3 LESIONS AND INVASIVE CANCER IN SELECTED CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDIES.

Author, year of publication, country of study	No. of participants	Women age group	Sensitivity % OF VIA	Specificity, % VIA
Carol et al, 2008, USA ⁽¹⁾	500	18 to 75 years	71%	82%
Surendra S. Shastri et al, 2004, India ⁽³⁵⁾	4039	30–65 years	86.7	88.4
Poli U R et al, 2015, India ⁽³⁶⁾	18869	26-65years	50%	80%
Battacharya A K et al, 2015, India ⁽³⁷⁾	300	18-60yeras	89%	87%

In all these studies large population studied and mainly age group above 50 years included. Sensitivity and specificity of VIA in these studies more than 50 % respectively.

LIMITATION OF STUDY

In this study, a population of clinic attendees served as the sample. We recognised that this cohort was not representative of the overall population, but we still approved of it due to the availability of women for screening and the anticipated increased prevalence of cervical neoplasia. It's unclear if this choice affected how sensitive the VIA in our residents. As women underwent VIA alone in this study.

Further hospitals and study participants should be involved in this study to support the results, along with other screening tests.

CONCLUSION

The accuracy of VIA results may be impacted by the presence of cervicitis. This finding may be especially significant in low-resource countries where cervical cancer screenings are more frequently conducted using visual inspection techniques. The incidence of cervical pre malignancy and malignancy lesions was 0.6% and 0.1% respectively in the population being studied with VIA. These findings have substantial consequences for the effective provision of services in cervical screening tests in settings with limited resources.

SUMMARY

The study entitled “INFERENCE OF VISUAL INSPECTION WITH ACETIC ACID ON CERVIX: A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY” was conducted in the department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, BLDE (DU) Shri B M Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura during the period 2021- 2022.

The AIM of study is to find cervical histopathologies in aceto-white areas as a result of VIA test of the cervix when acetic acid applied.

The study included 880 women, age of 30-49 years, selected from screening programs conducted by Obstetrics and Gynaecology department after taking consent and detail history 880 women underwent per vaginal examination and visual inspection with acetic acid was done. VIA positive women underwent biopsy under aseptic condition.

Results was incidence of VIA positive was 8.4%, in that incidence of chronic cervicitis was 7 % respectively. Incidence of premalignant lesion was 0.6%. Incidence of cervical carcinoma was 0.1%. The factors associated with a positive VIA was cervicitis.

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ANNEXURES

ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

B.L.D.E. (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY) IEC/NO-09/2021
Date-22/01/2021
(Declared vide notification No. F.3-37/2007-U.3 (A) Dated: 29-2-2008 of the MHRD, Government of India under Section 5 of The UGC Act, 1956)
The Constituent College
SHRI. B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH CENTRE

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Institutional ethical committee of this college met on 11-01-2021 at 11-00 am to scrutinize the synopsis of Postgraduate students of this college from Ethical Clearance point of view. After scrutiny the following original/corrected and revised version synopsis of the Thesis has been accorded Ethical Clearance

Title: Inference of visual inspection with acetic acid on cervix: A cross sectional study

Name of PG student: Dr Vaishnavi Malji, Department of Obst/Gynaec

Name of Guide/Co-investigator: Dr Shailaja.R.Bidri, Professor of Obst/Gynaec

DR. S.V. PATIL
CHAIRMAN, IEC

Institutional Ethical Committee
B.L.D.E. (Deemed to be University)
Shri B.M. Patil Medical College,
VIJAYAPUR-586103 (Karnataka)

Following documents were placed before Ethical Committee for Scrutinization:

1. Copy of Synopsis / Research project
2. Copy of informed consent form
3. Any other relevant documents.

11

INFORMED CONSENT FOR PARTICIPATION IN DISSERTATION / RESEARCH

I, the undersigned, _____, D/O W/O _____, aged _____ years, ordinarily resident of _____ do hereby state/declare that Dr VAISHNAVI MALJI of Shri. B. M. Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre has examined me thoroughly on _____ at _____ (place) and it has been explained to me in my own language that I am suffering from _____ disease (condition) and this disease/condition mimic following diseases. Further Dr VAISHNAVI MALJI informed me that he/she is conducting dissertation/research titled “Inference of visual inspection with acetic acid on cervix: A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY” under the guidance of Dr. SHAILAJA R BIDRI and co-guide DR. SUREKHA. B. HIPPARGI requesting my participation in the study. Apart from routine treatment procedure, the pre-operative, operative, post-operative and follow-up observations will be utilized for the study as reference data. Doctor has also informed me that during conduct of this procedure like adverse results may be encountered. Among the above complications most of them are treatable but are not anticipated hence there is chance of aggravation of my condition and in rare circumstances it may prove fatal in spite of anticipated diagnosis and best treatment made available. Further Doctor has informed me that my participation in this study would help in evaluation of the results of the study which is useful reference to treatment of

other similar cases in near future, and also I may be benefited in getting relieved of suffering or cure of the disease I am suffering.

The Doctor has also informed me that information given by me, observations made. Photographs video graphs taken upon me by the investigator will be kept secret and not assessed by the person other than me or my legal hirer except for academic purposes.

The Doctor did inform me that though my participation is purely voluntary, based on information given by me, I can ask any clarification during the course of treatment / study related to diagnosis, procedure of treatment, result of treatment or prognosis. At the same time I have been informed that I can withdraw from my participation in this study at any time if I want or the investigator can terminate me from the study at any time from the study but not the procedure of treatment and follow-up unless I request to be discharged.

After understanding the nature of dissertation or research, diagnosis made, mode of treatment, I the undersigned Smt _____ under my full conscious state of mind agree to participate in the said research/dissertation.

Signature of patient:

Signature of doctor:

Date:

Place

OBSTETRIC HISTORY:

PAST HISTORY:

PERSONAL HISTORY:

GENERAL PHYSICAL EXAMINATION:

PALLOR: TEMPERATURE: PULSE: BLOOD PRESSURE:

CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM /RESPIRATORY SYSTEM :

PER ABDOMEN:

PER SPECULUM EXAMINATION :

VIA :

BIOPSY REPORT:

STUDY NUMBER	NAME	MARRIED LIFE in years AGE in years	ADDRESS	1ST DATE OF MENSTRUAL PERIOD	LIVING PARA	DEATH	ABORTION	TUBECTOMISED	VAGINALLY / CAESAREAN	PAST HISTORY	PERSONAL HISTORY	GENERAL PHYSICAL EXAMINATION	PER ABDOMEN	CERVICAL AND VAGINA HEALTHY	CERVICAL EROSION	CERVICAL HYPERTROPHY	VAGINITIS	WHITE DISCHARGE	VIA
1	SHOBHA	30 10	VIJAYPURA	15 3	3	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
2	MAHANANDA	49 25	VIJAYPURA	13 6	2	4	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	YES	NO	NEGATIVE	
3	LALITHABAI	46 30	VIJAYPURA	9 2	1	0	1	CAESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
4	SOUMYA	34 16	INDI	17 1	1	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	ABETES MELLITUS SINCE	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
5	RENUKA	30 10	KOLLAR	15 2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
6	MAHADEVI	49 25	AGARKHED	12 2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
7	VILASMATI	30 13	KOLLAR	20 1	1	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
8	INDURATHOD	36 16	AGARKHED	7 3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
9	USHA	32 10	TALIKOTI	22 2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
10	PREMA	34 9	MUDHOL	19 1	1	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	YES	NO	NEGATIVE	
11	INDU	34 16	VIJAYPURA	15 3	1	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
12	VANITA	35 12	VIJAYPURA	15 2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
13	YASHODHA	36 12	VIJAYPURA	13 2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
14	ANNURADHA	37 20	KANNUR	18 6	4	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE
15	NURJANA	32 14	TAKKE	21 2	2	6	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
16	GEETA	32 8	ARJUNGI	17 1	1	3	0	CAESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
17	FULABAI	43 26	VIJAYPURA	9 2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
18	SATAVIVA	38 20	KOLLAR	10 3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
19	MAHADEVI	32 15	VIJAYPURA	31 3	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
20	REKHA	32 12	VIJAYPURA	23 2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
21	SAROJINI NAIK	44 30	VIJAYPURA	28 3	3	0	0	CAESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	NEGATIVE	
22	ARATI	45 20	KOLLAR	12 2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
23	SANGEETA	30 10	INCHAGERI	21 3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
24	SIDDAMMA	30 10	SHIVANAGI	13 2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
25	ARATI PUJARI	35 16	NAGARAL	22 3	3	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE
26	SHASHIKALA	49 29	ITTANGHAL	13 3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
27	RESHMA	30 12	INDI	21 2	2	2	0	CAESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE	
28	JAYASHREE	30 10	INCHAGERI	6 3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
29	MAHADEVI	30 12	INDI	12 2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	HT APPENDECTOMY	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
30	BHAGYASHREE	30 4	SINDGI	20 2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
31	GEETA	30 8	INDI	15 1	1	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
32	MAYAVVA HINJI	30 6	ALMEL	8 1	1	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
33	SUVRINADEVI HF	30 7	INDI	16 2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE
34	SUVARNADEVI	35 15	INDI	15 2	2	3	0	CAESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE
35	MUTTAVVA	35 16	ARAKERI	13 2	2	0	0	CAESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE
36	MALLAMMA	40 22	ARAKERI	15 3	3	0	0	CAESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE
37	YASAMINI	32 14	ALMEL	12 3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE
38	RENUKA	33 15	INCHAGERI	13 3	3	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
39	AKKAMAHADEVI	35 15	SINDGI	16 3	3	0	0	CAESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
40	LAJIMBAI	46 26	ALMEL	13 2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE
41	SANITA	37 17	ARAKERI	18 3	2	3	1	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
42	DIKSITA	36 12	INCHAGERI	20 2	2	2	0	CAESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE	
43	VAISHALI	30 10	INDI	21 2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE
44	SUJATA	45 25	VIJAYPURA	8 2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE
45	PARVATI	37 17	ACHERI	15 3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE
46	GOURABAI	49 25	HANCHANAL	18 2	2	3	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA
47	TULSABAIRATH	49 30	KANNUR	10 0	0	0	0	NOT DELIVERED	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
48	RAMEJA	47 27	BALLOLI	16 3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
49	LATHA	46 26	AGARKHED	18 3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
50	ANJALI	31 12	HANCHANAL	19 2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
51	MARJULA	30 12	HORTI	20 2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	LEFT OOPHARECTOMY	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
52	JAYANTI	45 27	AGARKHED	19 3	3	0	0	CAESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
53	ASHVINI	44 24	KOTYAL	20 3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
54	KALAWATI	34 15	HITNALLI	8 3	3	0	0	CAESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
55	GAIATRI	46 28	KOTYAL	15 3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
56	BHARTI	45 25	HITNALLI	12 3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
57	PREMA	38 15	AGARKHED	20 3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
58	NOORJAN	30 4	AGARKHED	18 2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
59	AMBKA	30 6	BALLOLI	20 3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
60	KAMALA	36 10	KOTYAL	12 2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SEVERE DYSPLASIA
61	MUZARIN	30 10	HITNALLI	8 2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
62	MEENAKSHI	39 12	INDI	18 3	3	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH MILD DYSPLASIA
63	SUNANDA	30 6	INDI	15 2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
64	SANITA	30 5	SINDGI	10 2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE	
65	SUNANDA	37 10	KOTYAL	15 2	2	1	0	CAESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
66	KAMALA	32 12	AGARKHED	20 2	2	1	0	CAESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
67	PRIVA	42 23	VIJAYPURA	18 3	3	2	0	CAESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
68	VIDYA	48 30	VIJAYPURA	12 2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE
69	PRATIBHA	35 15	ARAKERI	10 2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
70	MARJULA	49 30	INDI	10 3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
71	RAJANI	45 27	INDI	10 2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
72	GOURI	30 12	BALLOLI	8 2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
73	REKHA	45 25	INDI	20 2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	

73	REKHA	45	25	INDI	20	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
74	SUMITRA	42	22	INDI	16	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
75	SUKANYA	45	20	SINDGI	10	3	3	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
76	PREMA	30	8	HITTHALI	10	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
77	MONIKA	30	8	INCHAGERI	15	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
78	SUMA	45	15	VJAYPURA	10	1	1	0	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
79	LATA	39	19	INDI	8	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
80	AMBRITA	45	16	INDI	10	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
81	SANVI	36	12	ARAKERI	12	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
82	SUNITA	40	12	VJAYPURA	15	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
83	PARAVATI	40	20	VJAYPURA	18	3	3	1	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS
84	MANGALA	38	18	MUDHOL	16	1	1	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
85	SAVITA	30	6	KOTYAL	10	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
86	LAXMI	45	25	TALIKOTI	15	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
87	NIRMALA	41	23	INCHAGERI	12	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
88	SUJATA	34	12	VJAYPURA	22	3	3	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
89	RENUKA	35	10	BALLOLI	12	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
90	AMBAVVA	45	26	INDI	15	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
91	NEELABAI	38	20	ARAKERI	15	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SOUAMOUS METAPLASIA
92	LAXMI	32	8	ARJUNGI	12	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
93	GEETA	34	14	INDI	10	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
94	SONABAI	40	20	ARAKERI	15	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
95	MAHADEVI	35	12	AHERI	10	3	3	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
96	SANGEETA	30	8	ARAKERI	15	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
97	SAVITRI	30	6	ARAKERI	10	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
98	PREMA	35	15	MUDEEBHAL	10	2	2	1	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES	NEGATIVE	
99	CHANDRAWVA	49	20	INDI	10	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	FAPILLARY ENDOCERVICITIS
100	SONABAI	48	20	VJAYPURA	8	6	6	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
101	SAVITRI	49	29	INDI	15	4	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	HYPERTENSION SINCE 3	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
102	SHARANAMMA	46	28	JEVOOR	18	5	4	2	1	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SOUAMOUS METAPLASIA
103	LAXMI	48	28	INCHAGERI	10	2	2	1	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES	NEGATIVE	
104	PARVATI	48	20	LONI	45	2	2	1	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
105	SHANTAVVA	48	30	HITTHALI	20	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
106	SHANTA	49	18	INDI	15	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
107	MAHADEVI	49	26	ARAKERI	15	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
108	ARATI	32	10	INDI	10	1	1	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
109	SHREDEVI	35	13	UKKALI	15	2	2	1	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
110	SHRADDDHA	32	10	NIDONI	15	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
111	LAGAVVA	49	19	INDI	20	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
112	KASTURI	48	18	KAKHANDAKI	15	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NT APPEDECTOMY TVE	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
113	HUSAINBANU	30	8	HANCHANAL	15	4	4	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
114	LAXMINGSALE	32	10	LONI	15	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
115	SUMAN	30	10	ARAKERI	15	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
116	ROOPA	35	15	BABANAGAR	15	2	2	2	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
117	MADHALAMMA	35	12	BALLOLI	10	3	3	2	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	FAPILLARY ENDOCERVICITIS
118	KASTURIBAI	45	25	KOTYAL	15	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
119	LAXMIBAI	39	20	INDI	15	3	3	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
120	VIMALA	46	26	SINDGI	15	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
121	MAHANANDA	38	20	BIJARGI	20	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
122	RAJESHWARI	38	19	KAKHANDAKI	20	2	2	2	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS
123	SHANTAMMA	33	13	NIDONI	15	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
124	LAXMILAMMA	40	20	INCHAGERI	15	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
125	RAJAMMA	30	10	KUDAGI	15	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
126	LAXMIVASTRAD	32	10	MANNUR	10	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
127	RAJESHWARI	35	15	DUDHAL	15	3	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
128	REKHA	30	10	DUDHAL	15	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
129	KALLAMMA	32	10	INDI	15	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
130	PUSHPA	32	8	KUDAGI	15	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
131	BIBUJAH	33	15	BABANAGAR	15	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
132	SHASHIKALA	33	10	ARAKERI	15	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
133	GANGAMMA	33	6	INCHAGERI	10	1	1	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
134	MUMTAZ	37	20	VJAYPURA	8	5	5	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	PLENECTOMY INDICATIC	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
135	NEELAMMA	38	20	KUDAGI	7	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
136	SHARADA	38	18	KAKHANDAKI	20	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
137	SIDDAMMA	35	15	JEVOOR	18	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
138	GIRIJA	47	27	INDI	19	3	3	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
139	PARVATI	30	10	KOTYAL	45	1	1	2	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE	
140	RATNA	45	25	ARAKERI	15	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
141	MAITRI	35	15	JEVOOR	20	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE	
142	YAMANAMMA	34	14	NIDONI	10	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
143	SAVITRI	33	15	LONI	20	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
144	SAVITRI	45	25	INDI	20	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
145	BHORAMMA	30	12	INCHAGERI	15	0	0	0	0	NOT DELIVEREI	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE	
146	GITA	33	15	DUDHAL	12	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
147	SAVITA	33	10	BIJARGI	23	4	4	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
148	RENUKA	32	14	BORMANALLI	12	4	4	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	

162	MALLAMMA	40	20	SASAIKALVIVI	7	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	HYPERTENSION SINCE 8	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
163	SARASWATI	29	20	BILGI	20	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE	
164	PARVATI	32	12	MUDHOL	22	2	2	1	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
165	NUSRATH	35	18	CHADCHAN	24	5	5	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
166	NINGAMMA	30	10	LONI	21	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
167	RASULABAI	30	6	ATHARGA	15	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
168	SUBAPPA	30	6	ARJUNGI	15	1	1	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
169	NAGHA	38	20	YATHAL	5	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
170	SARASWATI	31	5	VJAYPURA	21	1	1	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
171	RENUKA	32	14	INDI	15	3	3	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
172	LAXMI	39	20	BIJJARGI	12	1	1	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
173	DILSHAD	30	10	MUDHOL	5	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
174	SHAVENTHERAM	49	20	VJAYPURA	18	3	3	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
175	NIRMALA	43	23	ITTANGIHAI	20	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
176	SATGAMMA	32	12	ARAKERI	6	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
177	NIRMALA	45	25	BOHMANALLI	21	8	8	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
178	KALSUN	36	16	KAKHANDAKI	16	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
179	ARATI	44	26	INDI	18	4	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
180	ANITA	32	14	KOTIAL	15	5	5	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
181	BHARATI	40	20	VJAYPURA	20	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
182	KAVITA	39	20	HANCHANAL	11	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
183	PRIYA	30	8	VJAYPURA	15	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
184	ANITA	30	6	VJAYPURA	19	4	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
185	SHIVULEELAMATHI	30	12	ITTANGIHAI	10	5	5	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
186	SHIVULEELA	32	12	HORTI	6	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
187	SANGEETA	32	14	VJAYPURA	8	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
188	NIRMALA	30	8	INDI	14	2	2	2	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
189	SHOBHA	30	12	HANCHANAL	32	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
190	PAVANI	34	16	TORANI	8	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
191	VANDANA	44	24	VJAYPURA	8	3	3	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
192	LAXMI	31	11	MUDHOL	15	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
193	PARAVATI	36	18	VJAYPURA	12	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
194	PARAVATI	45	26	VJAYPURA	16	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
195	PATITRA	32	10	VJAYPURA	19	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	POSITIVE
196	LAXMI	30	4	VJAYPURA	6	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
197	SUMITRA	40	21	TORANI	18	5	4	1	1	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
198	UMA	36	18	BIJJARGI	20	3	4	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
199	SHREEDEVIPTI	43	25	VJAYPURA	8	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	HYPOTHYROIDISM SINCE	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
200	REKHA BIRADAF	30	13	VJAYPURA	18	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
201	RENUKA BIRADAF	35	16	VJAYPURA	8	1	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
202	SHANAZ USTAD	33	16	VJAYPURA	10	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
203	MARADEVI	39	22	MUDEBBEHAL	6	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	NEGATIVE	
204	PRAVEEN USTAD	38	18	KALAGI	20	1	1	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
205	SIDDAMMA	44	21	VJAYPURA	8	5	4	0	1	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
206	RENUKA KOTI	45	30	BIJJARGI	20	3	2	0	1	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
207	GANGABAI HAHM	32	12	AINAPUR	15	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEX	NEGATIVE
208	BIRAMA	30	10	VJAYPURA	14	4	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
209	BHARATI	30	10	VJAYPURA	13	2	2	3	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
210	SHIVAGANGAMI	36	12	VJAYPURA	23	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
211	JAINABAI	38	18	VJAYPURA	18	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
212	KALAVATI	49	25	VJAYPURA	10	4	0	0	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	POSITIVE	
213	GOURAMMA	37	17	VJAYPURA	4	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
214	HANAMAMAYYA	37	19	VJAYPURA	9	2	1	0	1	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
215	SAWITRI	41	22	MUDEBBEHAL	75	3	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	
216	KALPANNA	30	12	ALLUR	10	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
217	DHANIYA	30	16	BALGANUR	30	2	2	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEX	NEGATIVE
218	SUMALATA	30	14	BILEBHAVI	8	1	1	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
219	POOJA	30	7	AHERI	6	2	2	2	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
220	AKSHATA	30	5	VJAYPURA	7	1	1	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	NEGATIVE	
221	HASEENA	30	3	ALMEL	8	0	0	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
222	LAXMIBAI	47	23	ARAKERI	10	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	POSITIVE	
223	SHRUTI	30	12	VJAYPURA	9	0	0	0	0	OT DELIVERED	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
224	KAVERI	30	10	VJAYPURA	6	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
225	IRAMMA	30	4	VJAYPURA	6	1	1	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
226	SAWITRI	38	18	ARAKERI	18	2	2	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
227	MANISHA	30	12	VJAYPURA	20	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
228	NAMITA	45	26	BILEBHAVI	8	4	2	3	2	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
229	SUDHA	44	24	AHERI	60	3	3	4	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
230	UMA	40	28	VJAYPURA	10	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	YES	RESEX	NEGATIVE
231	ANITA	36	16	ALMEL	12	3	3	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
232	LAXMI	30	10	ARAKERI	12	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
233	PRATIBHA	40	30	VJAYPURA	100	2	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
234	SWATI	30	12	VJAYPURA	15	1	1	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
235	SHILPA	36	16	VJAYPURA	21	2	2	3	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
236	RAJESHWARI	48	28	ARAKERI	88	3	2	1	1	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE	
237	PREMA	40	21	VJAYPURA	28	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
238	NEELAMMA	40	22	BILEBHAVI	22	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEX	NEGATIVE
239	NAYANA	44	24	AHERI	135	1	1	3	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
240	KOUSHALYA	30	12	VJAYPURA	23	1	1	0	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
241	KAJAL	30	10	ALMEL	26	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
242	DEEPA																				

251	MANJULA	30	6	INDI	6	1	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
252	MAHADEVI	49	31	IRAKAL	19	3	3	1	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS
253	DANAMMA	39	21	INDI	5	1	1	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
254	MANJULA	32	9	INCHAGERI	19	2	2	1	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
255	SALEEMA	42	12	HORTI	26	3	3	1	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
256	GEETA	45	25	HEBSHAL	90	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
257	SUREKHA	30	3	BOHMANALLI	27	1	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
258	SHARADA	35	18	BIJJARGI	23	2	2	3	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
259	JOBEDA	30	12	KOTYAL	32	2	2	1	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
260	MAHADEVI	30	4	KANNUR	15	1	1	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
261	KANITA	32	10	KITTUR	19	1	1	2	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
262	ARATI	34	14	VJAYIPURA	20	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
263	SHOBA	40	20	VJAYIPURA	8	3	3	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
264	KANITA	33	6	VJAYIPURA	12	1	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
265	NOORJAH	37	12	SINDGI	20	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS
266	MAHADEVI	46	16	KOLAR	16	4	4	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS
267	LAJMI	30	6	VJAYIPURA	23	2	2	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
268	NEENAKSHI	36	18	HARAKERI	17	3	2	1	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
269	JAGADEVI	49	29	MADASANAL	##	2	2	3	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
270	SUMITRA	30	12	VJAYIPURA	20	4	4	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
271	USHA	40	22	ALUR	26	2	2	2	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
272	MEGHA	32	8	VJAYIPURA	8	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
273	MANJULA	30	7	AGARKHED	20	1	1	2	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
274	VEENA	48	30	GUNAKI	120	2	2	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
275	PARVIN	30	12	KANNUR	15	1	1	2	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
276	PREETI	32	14	KOTYAL	19	2	2	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
277	GANGA	40	22	VJAYIPURA	16	2	2	1	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
278	ARATI	48	18	NAGATHAN	26	1	1	1	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
279	KALAVATI	36	18	SARAWAD	90	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
280	HARINI	36	18	INDI	15	3	3	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
281	ANITA	36	15	KANNUR	32	2	1	2	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
282	DANAWVA	36	12	HIPPARGI	36	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
283	SAWITA	38	20	KOTYAL	18	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
284	SHRIDEVI	35	15	KANNUR	30	2	2	2	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
285	PREMA	39	19	INDI	10	3	3	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
286	SHWETA	49	29	INDI	26	3	3	1	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
287	GIRIJA KAJOL	46	28	KOTYAL	15	3	3	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE	
288	GAYATRI BALOLI	35	18	KANNUR	25	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
289	JAYASHRI	43	23	VJAYIPURA	20	2	2	2	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
290	BHARATI	44	24	AINHAF	8	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
291	SUMITRA	48	30	BABALESHWAR	15	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE	
292	RASZULABAI	40	22	INDI	45	3	3	2	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
293	HALLYAMMA	45	28	MUDEBIBHAL	20	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	POSITIVE	WELL DIFFERENTIATED SQUAMOUS CELL CARCINOMA
294	UMA	36	18	KANNUR	18	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
295	GIRIJA	45	25	KOTYAL	23	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
296	GORAMMA	44	26	JAMBAGI	15	4	4	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
297	HASSEENA	30	10	YATHAL	13	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
298	LATTA	30	10	VJAYIPURA	12	1	1	2	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
299	SUNANDA	45	25	YAKKUNDI	10	3	3	2	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	YES	NEGATIVE	
300	SHANTABAI	49	25	TIKOTA	10	2	2	2	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
301	HEMA	39	19	TORAH	15	2	2	1	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
302	PREMA	33	15	SHEGUNSHI	15	3	3	1	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
303	ANITA	32	10	SHEGUNSHI	15	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
304	SHANTAMMA	47	27	KANNUR	10	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
305	SHASHIKALA	35	15	INCHAGERI	16	4	4	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
306	MILABAI	45	20	SINDGI	10	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
307	ROOPAM	33	10	SURPUR	8	1	1	3	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
308	SHANTABAI	45	20	VJAYIPURA	17	4	4	2	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
309	HAFLZABAHU	47	18	KOTYAL	12	2	2	2	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
310	DEVAKI	30	15	MUDEBIBHAL	8	4	4	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
311	LAKSHMI	41	18	INCHAGERI	12	2	2	2	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
312	AMBIKA	33	12	VJAYIPURA	16	1	1	2	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
313	YALLAMMA	30	10	SINDGI	6	3	3	1	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
314	DANESHWARI	48	24	INDI	22	3	3	1	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
315	SAGUBAI	49	22	ITTANGHAL	28	3	3	1	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
316	SHARUBAI	38	18	INDI	14	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
317	GOURAMMA	36	10	SINDGI	19	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
318	JYOTI	40	15	MUDEBIBHAL	20	1	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
319	HEMA	42	18	ARAKERI	12	5	4	1	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
320	BOURAMMA	45	25	INDI	8	4	4	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
321	SUNITA	38	20	INDI	23	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
322	MALAN	40	22	BALLOLI	19	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
323	MAIRUN	36	16	ARAKERI	8	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
324	SUNANDA	32	10	MUDEBIBHAL	17	1	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
325	BHARATI	38	17	KOTYAL	27	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
326	SMITA	35	17	ARAKERI	20	2	2	2	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
327	SUNANDA	40	22	KOTYAL	20	4	4	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
328	CHANDRAWVA	45	22	INCHAGERI	12	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
329	SUSHMA	44	20	NIDONI	8	4	4	2	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS
330	REKHA	45	22	VJAYIPURA	17	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
331	BHINMABHAI	45	14	NIDONI	11	1	1	2	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
332	SHAKUNTALA	45	30	MUDEBIBHAL	12	0	0	0	NOT DELIVERED	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
333	BORRABAI	30	10	MUDEBIBHAL	10	5	5	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT								

340	RANJITA	33	26	HONAVAD	15	3	3	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
341	MALLAMA	30	12	ARAKERI	9	3	3	1	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
342	SAHITA	40	22	BARALESHWAR	15	2	2	0	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
343	BHAGYASHREE	30	20	BARNAGAR	12	2	2	0	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEP	NEGATIVE
344	SANGEETA	36	16	ARJUNGI	10	2	2	0	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
345	NAGAMMA	32	13	ARJUNGI	12	3	3	0	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
346	HARSHITA	32	14	HANCHANAL	14	2	2	0	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
347	SWATI	34	14	GONASANGI	45	3	3	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
348	PRATHIBA	41	21	BARATAGI	16	1	1	0	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
349	BHARATI	39	20	JAINAPUR	10	3	3	0	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
350	VEENA	40	20	INDI	15	3	3	0	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
351	SHIVAGANDA	37	17	INDI	15	3	3	0	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS PAPILLARY ENDOCERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA
352	UMMA	41	20	UKKALI	10	3	3	0	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
353	YAMINI	36	16	ITTANALI	10	4	4	0	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
354	KAVIERI	37	18	VJAYPURA	10	3	3	0	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
355	SUNANDA	41	20	SARAWAD	16	2	2	2	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
356	RAJASHREE	45	15	ITTANALI	10	3	3	0	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
357	KASTURIBAI	30	8	ITTANALI	15	3	3	1	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
358	SANGEETA	30	12	SARAWAD	20	3	3	1	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
359	PITALABI	49	14	JAINAPUR	21	3	3	1	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
360	RESHMA	35	15	MAMDAPUR	13	3	3	2	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
361	SARASWATI	49	20	HONAVAD	75	3	3	0	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
362	MAHESHWARI	37	17	DEVAPUR	18	2	2	2	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
363	SOUMYA	35	15	KAVHIPPARAG	15	3	3	1	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEP	NEGATIVE
364	NAGAMMA	40	20	BELLUBI	22	2	2	2	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
365	MALATHI	36	16	HITTANALI	19	3	3	1	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
366	REVATI	39	20	DOMANHAL	12	3	3	2	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO	NEGATIVE
367	LAKSHI	30	10	BARANAGAR	8	2	2	1	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
368	NIRMALA	40	20	ARAKERI	10	3	3	0	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
369	SIVIDHA	39	17	BELLUBI	12	2	2	2	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
370	CHAYA	37	17	GUNAKI	15	2	2	1	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
371	SUNANDA	30	10	HONAVAD	10	2	2	2	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
372	KALPANNA	30	10	ITANGHAL	15	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
373	SUVARNA	30	10	VJAYPURA	15	2	2	1	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
374	UMMA	30	10	JAINAPUR	12	2	2	1	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
375	AMEENA NAGAT	30	8	MADASANAL	10	3	3	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
376	SAHITA	34	14	MAMDAPUR	18	2	2	1	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
377	MANTAZ	35	15	NIDONI	15	2	2	2	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
378	LALITHA	40	20	YATHAL	10	2	2	1	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
379	TRIVENI	35	15	AGARKHED	15	3	3	1	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
380	KAVITA	42	20	KUDAGI	10	3	3	2	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS
381	BASAMA KORI	30	10	JEVOOR	19	3	3	2	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
382	RADHA BADISET	34	14	HANCHANAL	8	4	4	0	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
383	LAKSHI	32	14	INCHAGEERI	10	0	0	0	0	NOT DELIVERED	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
384	BASAMA	30	10	LONI	10	0	0	0	0	NOT DELIVERED	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
385	PRIVAMANI	35	15	KEMINGHAL	20	1	1	3	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
386	RANI	30	10	LONI	18	2	2	0	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
387	SOUHYA YALAGI	40	20	INDI	10	2	2	0	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
388	PADMINI	35	15	BUDHAL	15	1	1	2	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
389	ROOPA MOLI	30	20	BALLOLI	18	2	2	0	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
390	VAISHALI	34	16	ARJUNGI	22	2	2	2	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
391	WATTIEDA	40	20	TALKKALAKI	16	0	0	0	0	NOT DELIVERED	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
392	TARUBAIRATHO	35	17	NAGATHAN	13	3	3	1	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
393	YASHODADOSA	45	25	KOTTAL	10	2	2	1	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
394	GIRIJA	30	20	KANABUR	12	2	2	0	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
395	MAHADEVI	40	20	ITANGHAL	10	2	2	2	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
396	LAKSHMIBAI PUJAF	46	26	ITANGHAL	10	2	2	1	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
397	OHAYTA	37	17	HONNALI	10	2	2	0	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
398	VEENA	46	26	BELLUBI	29	2	2	2	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
399	NAGAMMA	43	23	BELLUBI	8	3	3	0	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
400	ANITA	35	15	VJAYPURA	7	3	3	2	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
401	ANUBAI	39	19	AINAPUR	8	2	2	2	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
402	SHILPA	32	6	AINAPUR	15	1	1	2	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
403	MADVI	49	20	BIJARGI	16	2	2	1	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
404	BASAMMA	36	18	DEVAPUR	6	2	2	3	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	RESEP	POSITIVE
405	LAKSHMIBAI	32	2	GONASANGI	20	2	2	1	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
406	SHARADA	40	20	HITTANALI	12	1	1	3	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
407	SHARIFA	40	20	ALYBAD	13	3	3	2	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
408	RENUKA KUMBA	30	7	ARAKERI	15	2	2	0	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
409	BASAMMA KORI	40	16	HONAVAD	45	2	2	1	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
410	GANGUBAI HOSI	40	12	MADASANAL	16	2	2	1	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
411	RITANA PATEL	30	8	SHIVNAGI	6	3	3	0	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
412	BASAMMA BAJJ	35	15	TORAVI	23	3	3	2	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
413	BASAMMA HOLY	33	10	AGARKHED	15	2	2	2	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
414	MEENAKSHI	37	17	CHADCHAN	45	3	3	2	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
415	TEENA SOMESHI	33	2	HALSANGI	60	1	1	0	0	VAGINALY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
416	SANGEETA	35	5	INCHAGEERI	16	2	2	0	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
417	FATHIMA	32	4	JEVOOR	12	0	0	0	0	NOT DELIVERED	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
418	MALATI	36	16	KOTTAL	17	2	2	1	0	VAGINALY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	

429	PREMAMANTOO	34	8	BASANAL	13	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
430	SUVARNA	47	17	TORAVI	13	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
431	REKHA	44	24	TAJAPUR	60	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
432	RATHANMA	41	21	SHIVHAGI	17	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
433	JYOTHIREMATH	37	17	SARAVAD	20	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
434	NEELAMMA	35	10	TALIKOTI	22	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
435	HANDBAIPATHI	35	10	INDI	15	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
436	SUMALATHA	31	10	HONAVAD	21	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
437	BHAGIRATHI	30	6	VJAYAPURA	20	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
438	SHOBHA CHAMF	40	18	VJAYAPURA	15	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
439	HIRHALAHANUR	36	10	ITANGHAL	15	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
440	MADINANADAF	35	10	BASANAL	15	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
441	ISHWARIPUJAR	30	6	VJAYAPURA	18	3	3	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
442	LAJIMBAIKUCHI	35	10	LONI	6	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
443	PARSUBAIBHAI	30	6	AINAPUR	12	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
444	LAJMI PADAGAR	30	4	MADASANAL	12	1	1	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
445	JYOTIRATHOD	30	10	TORAVI	10	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
446	SHANTANAI	30	6	SHIVHAGI	16	1	1	3	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
447	DRAKSHAYINI	38	18	TAJAPUR	16	2	2	3	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEX	NEGATIVE
448	SUNANDA RATH	40	16	HALASANGI	20	2	2	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
449	SHANTABAI	45	15	GORNALI	17	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE
450	SUNAHAYAK	35	15	BHARGI	5	4	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
451	SAWITA MAHE	44	25	GONASAGI	6	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
452	MAHADEVI	40	20	ITANGHAL	18	3	3	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
453	AKSHATA	44	14	BABANAGAR	17	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
454	SUVARNA HATTI	45	15	SAVANBAGEVH	23	1	1	3	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
455	POOJA JOSHI	48	18	INDI	20	3	3	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
456	DEEPA LAMANI	38	10	YAGIRI	10	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
457	SHRUTI GOYANK	34	14	MUDDHOL	12	2	2	2	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
458	PAWITRA METRI	33	10	GULABARGA	2	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
459	VIDYA KANNUR	40	20	YATHAL	20	1	1	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
460	SHAILA SURESH	42	20	ITANGHAL	15	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
461	SUNANDA KOPP	32	10	HONAVAD	12	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
462	IMHAMABEE GAI	46	26	ALMATTI	15	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
463	USHA CHAIAN	35	15	MUDDHOL	4	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
464	SHANUBAI CHAI	30	10	KOLAR	15	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
465	MOHINI TOSHI	48	28	ATTANI	10	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
466	SIDDAPPA HADA	49	25	CHADACHAN	15	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
467	GANGAIBAI FANI	45	23	BHUYAR	15	2	2	2	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
468	LAJIMBAI JADAI	42	22	INDI	10	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
469	LALITA CHAIYAN	48	18	SINDAGI	14	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
470	SAWITA CHAIYAN	31	10	AINAPUR	15	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
471	PATALAGIRATHI	49	29	SARNAD	10	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
472	SUVARNA KAPA	42	20	VJAYAPURA	15	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
473	JYOTI PAVAR	30	8	HANCHANAL	15	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
474	MAHANANDA BA	30	6	HITTHALI	2	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
475	BHIMABAI BADI	35	15	HALASANGI	18	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	NO	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
476	KAMLABAIVAI	40	15	AGARKHED	16	1	1	5	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	NO	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
477	ANJALI CHAIYAN	30	12	TALIKOTI	20	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
478	LAJIMDOTI	30	10	BHUYAR	13	1	1	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
479	JAYASHREE BISI	30	12	INDI	16	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEX	NEGATIVE
480	CHAITA	35	10	ALMATTI	8	3	3	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
481	RATHA	48	28	VJAYAPURA	18	3	3	2	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
482	POTALABAI	48	28	AINAPUR	18	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE
483	PAVANI	40	20	BHUYAR	28	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
484	GIRIJA	48	26	JHANAKHAND	6	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEX	NEGATIVE
485	ARATHI	35	16	TIKOTA	10	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
486	JAYASHREE	49	30	ATHANI	12	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
487	SUGALABAI	45	23	INDI	3	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
488	CHANDRIKA	30	6	SHIVHAGI	6	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
489	BAGAMMA	42	24	YATHAL	23	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
490	SHAKUNTALA	30	12	TORVI	21	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
491	GIRIJA	49	21	ITANGHAL	18	3	3	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
492	KAMALA	36	16	BABANAGAR	22	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
493	SAVITRI	30	8	BABALASHWAF	12	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
494	NEETARAMESH	47	27	SAVANBAGEVH	10	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
495	ROOPA	41	18	SINDAGI	18	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
496	ANJALI																				

519	THARABAI	45	25	SINDAGI	15	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
520	KASHIBAI	40	20	VUJAYAPURA	10	3	3	2	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
521	SAWITRAMMA	43	20	VUJAYAPURA	12	2	2	1	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
522	SHOBHA	45	26	INDI	15	2	2	2	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
523	MAHADEVI	30	10	INDI	15	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
524	SHANTI	33	13	SHIVANAGI	12	2	2	2	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
525	FARZANA	30	8	INDI	16	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
526	LALITHA	32	12	TIKOTA	12	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
527	SHANSHAD	35	15	INCHAGERI	10	3	5	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
528	KAVITA CHAVAN	30	12	JAINAPUR	8	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
529	RISHMA CHAYA	30	18	INDI	26	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
530	CHANDIBAI CHA	30	12	INCHAGERI	15	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
531	KASTURI	34	18	TIKOTA	15	2	2	2	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
532	SHANTHAMMA JIF	32	14	TIKOTA	23	2	2	3	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	NO	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
533	GEETABAI CHAV	30	9	INCHAGERI	18	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
534	SHANTHAMMA DE	35	12	AINAPUR	18	2	2	1	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
535	LAINIBAI CHAV	35	14	JAINAPUR	15	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
536	MAHTAMMA	40	20	INDI	16	3	3	0	CEASAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
537	HANAMMA JALI	38	20	ARAKERI	14	2	2	1	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
538	MALLAMMA KAT	35	15	BELLURI	16	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
539	CHANDRAMMA CI	45	15	BARATAGI	35	0	0	0	NOT DELIVERED	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
540	MARITAMA KATTI	40	10	TALIKOTI	15	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	
541	MALLAMMA NAV	30	8	KOTIAL	12	2	2	2	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
542	RENUKA BIRADP	35	16	NAGATHAN	45	2	2	2	0	CEASAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
543	KASHIBAI GURK	31	13	SHEGUNSHI	10	2	2	1	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
544	SAWITRI DURIEG	35	13	SIDDAPUR	15	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
545	SHRADHA YADH	30	8	GORNAL	30	3	3	1	0	CEASAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
546	PARAMMAVA	30	18	KERUSA	15	1	1	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
547	RENUKA THAMA	38	15	KOTIAL	29	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
548	DEVAMMA BAYA	30	10	MANNUR	15	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
549	RENUKA HIREMA	30	20	JEVOR	16	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
550	ANAPURNA HED	37	13	BHUYAR	10	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
551	RENUKA YARIKA	33	14	TAJAPUR	8	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
552	MEENAKSHI	38	18	SHEGUNSHI	18	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
553	GURUBAI	40	22	NAGATHAN	8	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
554	DEVAMMA	32	10	KUMATAGI	16	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEX	NEGATIVE
555	SUGHANDBA	38	20	HONNALI	16	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
556	SHOBHA	38	18	DUDHAL	23	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
557	SHASHIKALAH	35	15	TALIKOTI	8	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	
558	SUJANANI	32	12	SOMNAL	13	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
559	ANAPURNA BIRI	45	27	HIRUR	18	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
560	GHINIBAI	35	15	BAHTUR	20	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
561	JYOTISHWANGA	32	14	HORATTI	14	3	3	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE
562	SHARADA	45	25	BAPPARGA	23	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	
563	BORAMMA REVIA	45	23	NAGUR	18	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
564	LAINIBAI NAGAI	47	27	HALATIVAD	30	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
565	NEELAMMA	35	17	HALATIVAD	20	3	3	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	NO	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
566	SUNANDA SARU	30	8	RAHPUR	8	3	3	2	0	CEASAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
567	KAVITARAMESH	30	10	KALAPUR	10	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
568	JAYASHREE PM	30	12	VESUGUR	15	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
569	RENUKA	31	13	KUPPI	15	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
570	NEELAMMA PUJ	35	17	ARIKERA	18	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
571	RANI SANJAYTA	31	13	YEKTAPUR	15	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
572	SHRUTIKATSEF	25	14	KEMBHANI	15	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
573	VALIMA GOGI	35	18	HUNSHAL	6	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
574	BHAGIRATHI PU	40	22	BARADOL	12	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
575	REBAI CHIMIGOL	32	13	HALASANGI	13	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
576	SARJINI HONNI	32	10	KOTIAL	10	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
577	SAWITRI HADAR	30	10	MASALI	10	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
578	LALABI	35	17	RUGGI	10	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
579	LALITA DODAMA	34	16	BANAHATTI	8	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
580	SANGAMMA	37	17	BABLESHWAR	10	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
581	ASHA	42	24	INDI	10	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
582	GANGABAI	34	16	SINDAGI	8	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE
583	SAIFA	45	24	OMMANAHALLI	10	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
584	BEETA	32	12	UKKALI	10	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
585	SUJATA TORAD	40	20	EVARAHIPPAR	15	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
586	MANJULANATHI	46	21	HANCHANAL	10	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
587	RASHMI PATIL	41	21	SAVANBAGEW	15	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO			

609	BHAGYASHREE	36	16	ARAKERI	8	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
610	SUNITARATHOD	36	16	INCHAGERI	18	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
611	SAVITARATHOD	35	15	BHANTUR	23	3	2	0	1	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	RESE	NEGATIVE
612	TANUJA BOSALE	30	10	SINDAGI	18	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
613	UMA SAJJAN	30	12	AGASANAL	18	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
614	PREMA	30	10	BALLOLI	8	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
615	CHANDRAVVA	49	20	INDI	26	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA
616	POOJA	41	23	HULLUR	8	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
617	SUDHA RAJAPU	43	23	MUDEBIBHAL	23	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
618	IRRAMMA	41	21	ABBHAL	23	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	HC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA WITH NABOTHIAN CYST
619	SUHASINI	45	25	KHANAPUR	8	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
620	TEENA	46	26	JEYOOR	8	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
621	KULUSUMA	40	20	HANCAHAL	21	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
622	SHOBHA	31	11	INDI	8	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	HO	YES	NO	NO	RESE	NEGATIVE	
623	GEETA	45	25	MUDEBIBHAL	8	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
624	SUVARNA	37	17	LOHI	25	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
625	BHUMIKA	37	17	SHIROL	8	2	2	2	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
626	MALATI PATIL	47	15	BABANAGAR	3	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
627	TAIYAVI LAMA	40	18	RUGGI	8	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
628	SULOCHANA	30	8	HUNASHITAL	30	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	HO	YES	NO	NO	RESE	NEGATIVE	
629	CHITRAMANE	35	17	WANDAL	18	2	1	2	1	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
630	AKKAMAHADEVI	39	19	ALKOPPA	17	3	2	2	1	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
631	RAJESHVARIHAI	41	23	HURINHALI	12	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESE	NEGATIVE	
632	VIJAYALAKSHI	43	23	WANDAL	32	3	2	0	1	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
633	IMHAMAREE	41	21	NIMBAL	20	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	HO	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	HC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA WITH NABOTHIAN CYST
634	NIRAMALA JATT	43	23	BUDIHAL	8	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	HO	YES	NO	NO	RESE	NEGATIVE	
635	FATIMANADAF	30	12	TIKOTA	12	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
636	LALITHALAGERI	30	8	ALUR	21	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
637	RANIMASALI	30	12	ATHARGA	15	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
638	RAJASHREE	35	15	ITAGGI	15	2	1	0	1	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
639	GOURINDI	30	10	YOMMANAHALL	20	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
640	IRAMMA	39	20	KUDAGI	17	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
641	LATA KANNUR	30	12	AGASANAL	17	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	HO	YES	NO	NO	RESE	NEGATIVE	
642	KAVYA SUNAGA	30	10	SINDGI	25	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	HO	YES	NO	NO	RESE	NEGATIVE	
643	MANJULA	34	16	ARAKERI	23	3	3	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
644	BORANMA KAMI	30	18	MUDEBIBHAL	26	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
645	NELAMA	44	22	SINDGI	21	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
646	MAHADEVI	49	27	INDI	19	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
647	NITTU	30	14	TALIKOTI	18	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	HO	YES	NO	NO	RESE	NEGATIVE	
648	ROOPA	40	18	ARJUNGI	9	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	HO	YES	YES	NO	RESE	NEGATIVE	
649	SUJATA	47	24	INDI	25	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
650	PRIYA	39	19	ALUR	22	2	2	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
651	HASEENA	35	13	BARADOL	17	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	HO	YES	NO	NO	RESE	NEGATIVE	
652	MANGALA	20	10	VIJAYAPURA	19	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
653	NIRMALA	36	16	BIJJARGI	19	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	HC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA WITH NABOTHIAN CYST
654	SUJATA	39	15	BELLUBI	21	3	3	2	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
655	REKHA	46	20	MUTTAGE	18	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
656	SUSHMA	34	12	BANNIHATTI	16	2	2	1	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
657	AHEENA	45	14	HONNALI	15	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
658	SANGEETA	38	16	MINAJAGI	16	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	RESE	NEGATIVE	
659	POONAMDEVI	48	12	JUMHAL	10	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
660	KASTURIBAI	40	15	VIJAYAPURA	6	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
661	RAJASHREE	38	16	VIJAYAPURA	15	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
662	KAMALARAJI	45	25	KAGGOD	8	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
663	SHANKARAMMA	45	27	SOHNAL	13	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	HO	YES	NO	NO	RESE	NEGATIVE	
664	PREMA	45	21	KARJOL	18	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
665	MADINALLAVVA	42	23	WANDAL	6	3	3	1	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	HO	YES	NO	NO	RESE	NEGATIVE	
666	VANDANNA PUA	34	14	MADASANAL	30	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
667	YASHODANAHAI	39	20	SARAWAD	18	1	1	2	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	HO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
668	PREMA	41	18	INDI	12	0	0	0	0	HOT DELIVERED	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
669	DEVIKISHIROL	45	30	VIJAYAPURA	17	2	1	0	1	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	NO SPECIFIC PATHOLOGY
670	JAGADEVI	39	20	JAINAPUR	13	4	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	HO	YES	NO	NO	RESE	NEGATIVE	
671	SAVITRI	45	28	ITTINGHAL	8	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	HO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
672	LATA	47	24	AINAPUR	20	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
673	SARITA	37	17	ATHANI	5	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
674	RUPALI	39	20	JAMAKHANDI	11	0	0	0	0	HOT DELIVERED	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
675	VEENA	31	12	BELLUBI	17	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
676	NETTA	24	20	AGARKHED	6	5	5	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
677	FATIMA	42	24	YATHAL	6	4	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
678	NAGAMMA	47	30	SUTGUNDI	8	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA
679	MEENAKSHI	47	26	INDI	18	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	HO	YES	NO	NO	RESE	NEGATIVE	
680	AMBIKA	43	25	ARAKERI	21	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
681	YALLAVIA	40	24	BALLOLI	23	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	HO	YES	NO	NO	RESE	NEGATIVE	
682	SHOBHA	30	10	KAGGOD	25	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	HO	YES	YES	NO	RESE	NEGATIVE	
683	PREHABAI	46	14	AGASANAL	20	2	2	2	0	CESAREAN	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	HO	YES	NO	NO	RESE	NEGATIVE	
684	KAMALARAJI	37	12	VIJAYAPURA	10	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	HC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA WITH NABOTHIAN CYST
685	GIRIJA	46	20	MUDEBIBHAL	9	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD								

698	SHASHIKALA	30	8	MINAJAGI	19	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
699	SUJATA	45	25	INCHAGEERI	15	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
700	RATHAMMA	49	25	INDI	30	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE
701	RENUKA	42	16	AGARAKHED	60	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
702	SUNANDA	31	12	VUJAYAPURA	14	2	2	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
703	LATHA	30	10	LOHI	10	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
704	HAZHEEN	31	11	INDI	25	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
705	SARASWATI	46	28	INDI	15	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
706	VEENA	31	8	ARAKERI	15	3	3	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
707	DEIVAMMA	35	12	BALLOLI	45	2	2	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
708	JAYASHREE	44	23	ARAKERI	17	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
709	SHUSHILABAI	49	29	MUTTAGE	16	1	1	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS
710	KASTURIBAI	40	17	LOHI	17	2	2	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	HC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA WITH NABOTHIAN CYST
711	JANAKI	42	18	BUDIHAI	16	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
712	LAKSHI	44	18	TAKKALAKI	8	2	2	2	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
713	SHILPA	39	10	VALGUR	20	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	YES	YES	RESEP	NEGATIVE
714	ANITA	41	21	NANDHAI	17	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
715	GOURI	42	22	HAGUR	6	2	2	1	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
716	ASHVINI	33	10	INDI	18	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
717	SHOBHA	30	22	SAYANBAGEVI	12	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
718	ASHA	42	22	VUJAYAPURA	21	2	2	1	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
719	SHANTAMMA	41	20	MUDEDEBIHAL	19	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE
720	LAVANYA	34	10	INCHAGEERI	23	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
721	SHOBHA	40	18	UKKALLI	25	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
722	BALUBAI	36	16	INDI	15	2	2	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
723	IANI	35	22	JAINAPUR	8	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
724	DEVAKI	41	23	VUJAYAPURA	9	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
725	DEEPA	41	18	INDI	20	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH MILD DYSPLASIA
726	SANGEETA	42	16	ARAKERI	27	0	0	0	0	NOT DELIVERED	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
727	DEVI	41	23	INCHAGEERI	13	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
728	FATIMA	46	13	BHANTUR	8	5	5	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
729	SAVITRI	40	30	SINDAGE	6	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
730	GANGABAI	36	10	AGASANAL	45	2	2	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	HC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA WITH NABOTHIAN CYST
731	REVATI	32	13	BALLOLI	40	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
732	SUKANYA	30	10	INDI	18	0	0	0	0	NOT DELIVERED	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
733	SHARADA	31	12	MULLUR	12	2	2	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
734	RAJASHREE	35	12	MUDEDEBIHAL	8	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
735	SHUSHILABAI	49	23	ABBIHAL	8	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
736	SARITA	45	25	KHANAPUR	18	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
737	SHEEVALEELA	40	28	JEVOR	20	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
738	SHANTAMMA	41	20	HANGHANAL	9	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE
739	SHASHIKALA	40	21	INDI	27	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	HC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA WITH NABOTHIAN CYST
740	SAVITRI	46	26	MUDEDEBIHAL	18	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
741	SONALI	37	20	LOHI	6	1	1	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
742	INDRABAI	33	10	SHIROL	20	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
743	SUMA	32	10	BABANAGAR	13	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
744	PRAHILA	38	18	RUGGI	18	2	2	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	YES	YES	RESEP	NEGATIVE
745	ANITA	40	28	HUNASHYAL	40	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
746	SAGARIKA	41	21	WANDAL	34	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
747	DEEPA	47	13	ALKOPPA	16	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
748	SHARIFAMMA	42	12	HURINHALI	37	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
749	RAJANI	40	22	WANDAL	18	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	YES	YES	RESEP	NEGATIVE
750	SUMA	30	8	NIBHAL	13	6	5	0	1	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
751	SHANUBAI	37	18	BUDIHAI	6	3	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
752	SUVARNA	30	18	TIKOTA	9	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS
753	GURUBAI	32	10	ALUR	22	3	3	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
754	KASHIBHAI	43	16	ATHARGA	9	1	1	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
755	HAMEEDA	34	15	ITAGGI	45	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
756	YANI	35	16	SOHMMAHALI	25	3	3	1	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
757	MALLAIIYA	30	7	KUDAGE	17	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
758	SHIVEETA	39	16	AGASANAL	7	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEP	NEGATIVE
759	GOURAMMA	44	8	SINDGI	13	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
760	PREMA	32	7	ARAKERI	15	3	3	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
761	SHARIFA	46	26	MUDEDEBIHAL	24	4	4	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA
762	NEELAVIYA	49	18	SINDGI	16	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	HC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA WITH NABOTHIAN CYST
763	JAYANTI	41	28	INDI	9	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEP	NEGATIVE
764	SAVITA	30	15	TALIKOTI	23	4	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
765	RAJASRI	30	10	ARJUNGI	5	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
766	MALLAIIYA	30	8	INDI	19	4	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
767	SHESHIREKHA	38	15	ALUR	34	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
768	SHAINAZ	32	12	BARADOL	19	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
769	DIVYA	31	8	VUJAYAPURA	28	4	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
770	NEETA	34	10	BIJJARGI	16	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	POSITIVE	HC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA WITH NABOTHIAN CYST
771	SUJATTA	35	20	BELLURI	25	1	1	3	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
772	KALAIYATI	44	7	MUTTAGE	19	3	3	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
773	JAMUNA	39	10	BAINHATTI	40	3	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE
774	SARALA	36	18	HONHALI	18	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE

788	SAROJA	47	27	ITTANGHAL	40	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
789	MALLAMMA	46	28	AINAPUR	23	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
790	JANAKI	46	28	ATHANI	14	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
791	AINAPURNA	45	9	JANAKHANI	27	2	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
792	SUNITA	44	28	BELLURI	12	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA WITH NABOTHIAN CYST	
793	KASTURI	46	28	AGARKHED	25	2	2	4	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
794	BHARATI	35	7	YATHAL	7	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
795	REKHA	33	6	SUTGUNDI	8	0	0	0	0	HOT DELIVEREE	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
796	SUKANYA	39	8	INDI	16	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
797	MANJULA	46	22	ARAKERI	15	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	PAPILLARY ENDOCERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA
798	PAVITRA	30	10	BALLOLI	6	2	2	2	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
799	ROOPA	46	26	KAGGOD	28	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS
800	DANISHA	40	24	AGASAHAL	27	3	2	0	1	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
801	KAVITA	47	20	VJAYPURA	23	2	2	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
802	KASHIBAI	32	8	MUDEBHAL	11	1	1	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
803	JANAKI	33	10	BALLOLI	18	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
804	JANAKI	30	14	ALUR	90	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
805	SANGEETA	35	10	BIJARGI	34	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
806	SAVITA	40	28	SINDGI	31	4	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
807	DIVYA	46	26	BANIHATTI	8	2	2	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
808	RAMYA	40	23	SARAHAD	23	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
809	NIRMALA	30	12	AGARKHED	8	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
810	IRAMMA	37	10	BABANAGAR	32	5	5	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
811	BAGAVATHA	30	10	KUDAGI	9	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
812	BABY	49	29	SHIROL	8	4	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA
813	BASAVVA	38	18	BARADOL	21	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS
814	NAGAMMA	41	20	SUTGUNDI	45	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS
815	SARASWATHI	36	8	MINAJGI	33	4	5	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
816	MAHANANDA	35	15	INCHAGERI	8	4	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
817	RAMYA	40	19	INDI	9	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
818	MAHADEVI	36	10	AGARKHED	16	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
819	PARVATI	44	24	VJAYPURA	21	4	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
820	PRIYA	34	14	LOHI	19	0	0	0	0	HOT DELIVEREE	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
821	PREMA	43	23	INDI	8	0	0	0	0	HOT DELIVEREE	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
822	CHANDRABAGH	43	14	INDI	16	4	4	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
823	YALLAMMA	36	16	ARAKERI	19	2	2	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS
824	MANJULA	40	10	BALLOLI	23	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
825	KAVITA	37	17	ARAKERI	36	3	3	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
826	VEENA	33	12	MUTTAGE	18	1	1	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
827	NAGAMMA	40	10	WANDAL	19	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
828	BHAGIRATHI	46	28	BUDIHAL	18	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS
829	MAHADEVI	40	18	TAKKALAKI	20	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
830	MANGALA	40	29	YALGUR	13	0	0	0	0	HOT DELIVEREE	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
831	INDRABAI	33	12	HANDIHAL	11	5	5	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
832	GOURI	35	12	HAGUR	19	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
833	SAGARI	45	15	INDI	9	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
834	MANJULA	35	27	SAVANABEGERE	49	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
835	MAHANANDA	45	29	VJAYAPURA	34	3	3	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
836	UMA	44	26	MUDEBHAL	22	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
837	PREMA	35	14	INCHAGERI	11	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
838	SAVANAMMA	46	22	URKALLI	19	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS
839	LALITA	34	14	INDI	22	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
840	RENUKA	39	20	JAINAPUR	27	3	3	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
841	RENUKA	40	29	VJAYAPURA	14	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
842	MANTAMMA	41	21	INDI	25	3	3	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
843	LADHI	35	15	ARAKERI	28	3	3	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
844	SAVITA	36	18	INCHAGERI	22	2	2	4	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
845	SUNANDA	40	23	BHANTUR	12	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
846	BISMILLA	31	12	SINDAGI	19	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
847	PRABHAVATI	30	7	AGASAHAL	20	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
848	JAYASHRI	49	23	BALLOLI	15	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
849	RUBINA	33	15	INDI	21	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	NO	ABETES MELLITUS SINCE	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
850	KALAVATI	30	17	HULLUR	7	1	1	2	0	VAGINALLY	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
851	JYANTI	40	20	MUDEBHAL	6	2	2	2	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
852	RENUKA	40	27	ABBIHAL	60	2	2	3	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	YES	YES	RESEX	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA
853	RESHMA	38	13	KHANAPUR	34	3	3	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
854	PADMAJA	38	15	JEYOOR	18	2	2	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS WITH SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA
855	SHILPA	40	22	HANCHANHAL	14	0	0	0	0	HOT DELIVEREE	NO	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
856	SHANTABAI	36	16	INDI	19	4	4	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
857	KAMALABAI	38	18	MUDEBHAL	26	2	2	2	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
858	BHIMABAI	46	26	LOHI	12	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
859	LADIMBAI	47	20	SHIROL	8	3	3	1	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
860	GURUBAI	46	20	BABANAGAR	20	2	2	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
861	RADHIKA	34	14	RUGGI	6	3	3	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	YES	RESEX	NEGATIVE	
862	OTAMAMMA	40	15	HUNASHIHAL	14	3	3	0	0	CESAREAN	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
863	NAHARATA	37	20	WANDAL	17	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	RESEX	NEGATIVE
864	ROOPA	32	10	ALKOPPA	18	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD								

877	MALLAMA	38	14	ARAKERI	16	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
878	BHARATI	32	10	MUDEBINHAL	4	3	3	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NEGATIVE	
879	SARASWATI	48	30	KAKANDAKI	9	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	CHRONIC NON SPECIFIC CERVICITIS
880	ANASUBAI	45	27	VIJAYPURA	17	2	2	0	0	VAGINALLY	YES	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NOTHING SIGNIFICANT	NAD	NAD	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	POSITIVE	PAPILLARY ENDOCERVICITIS